

PREDICT 6G

D1.3

Final PREDICT-6G specification, techno-economic analysis, and guidelines for migrating to 6G scenarios

TID

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Authors	Sebastian Robitzsch, Chathura Sarathchandra, Renan Krishna (IDE) Pietro G. Giardina, Matteo Ravalli, Juan Brenes (NXW) Claudio Casetti, Guido Marchetto, Riccardo Sisto (POLITO) Péter Szilágyi, Tamás Kárász, Szabolcs Nováczki, Zoltán Vincze, Csaba Vulkán (NOK) Rafael Rosales, Valerio Frascolla (INT) Luis M. Contreras, Marta Blanco (TID) Luis Velasco, Salvatore Spadaro (UPC) Jose Luis Cárcel (ATOS) Jessica Carneiro (AUS) Antonio de la Oliva (UC3M)
Reviewers	Antonio de la Oliva (UC3M). Péter Szilágyi (NOK), Luis M. Contreras (TID)

Abstract

This document presents the final specification, techno-economic analysis, and migration guidelines for the PREDICT-6G project, which aims to develop a secure, interoperable, and scalable deterministic network architecture for 6G scenarios. It addresses key challenges in multi-domain, multi-technology networks by integrating a multi-domain data plane (MDP) and AI-driven multi-stakeholder inter-domain control plane (AICP) to enable end-to-end

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deterministic services with enhanced security, reliability, and automation. The techno-economic analysis demonstrates significant cost savings and business opportunities, particularly in smart manufacturing, by reducing total cost of ownership and improving operational efficiency. Migration guidelines provide a phased approach for integrating PREDICT-6G into existing infrastructures, ensuring compatibility and scalability while maintaining strong security measures. Overall, the project contributes to the advancement of 6G technology and supports Europe’s strategic goals in digital sovereignty and industrial competitiveness

Keywords

Security, business models, techno-economic, migration guidelines

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Acronyms and definitions

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DoA	Description of Action
WP	Work Package
E2E	End-to-End
MDP	Multi-domain Data-Plane
AICP	AI-driven Multi-stakeholder Inter-domain Control-Plane
DT	Digital Twin
ML	Machine Learning
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer

Table of partners

Short Name	Partner
UC3M	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
NOK	Nokia Solutions and Networks KFT
ERC	Ericsson Espana SA
INT	Intel Deutschland GMBH
TID	Telefonica Innovación Digital
ATOS	ATOS IT Solutions and Services Iberia SL
GES	Gestamp Servicios SA
NXW	Nextworks
COG	Cognitive Innovations Private Company
SIM	Software Imagination & Vision SRL
AUSTRALO	AUSTRALO Interinnov Marketing Lab
POLITO	Politecnico di Torino
UPC	Universitat Politecnica de Catalunya
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
UNIPD	Universita degli Studi di Padova
IDE	Interdigital Europe LTD

1 Executive summary

This deliverable presents the final specification of the PREDICT-6G system architecture, focusing on the security framework, techno-economic analysis, and migration guidelines essential for the transition to 6G networks. Grounded in the innovations developed throughout the project, it addresses the critical need for deterministic, secure, and efficient communication in multi-domain, multi-technology environments that characterize future 6G scenarios.

Chapter 3 details the core security elements integrated within the PREDICT-6G architecture. It introduces robust mechanisms such as inter-domain authentication leveraging distributed ledger technologies to replace traditional Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) with a more lightweight and efficient Pre-Shared Key (PSK) mechanism. This approach enhances security while reducing overhead and latency. The document further explores message protection through Message Authentication Codes (MAC) and discusses the challenges of integrating MACsec with Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN), highlighting the balance between security and strict timing constraints. A pivotal contribution is the multi-layer Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) redundancy strategy combined with an intelligent Path Computation Engine (PCE) based on Graph Theory. The PCE proactively computes and stores optimal network paths, enabling rapid failover and load balancing across both classical 3GPP and 3GPP enhanced Deterministic Networking (DetNet) architectures. Queueing theory-based performance evaluations demonstrate significant improvements in latency and packet loss reduction, underpinning the system's capacity to deliver ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC).

The chapter also addresses the securitization of AI components within the AI-driven Multi-stakeholder Inter-domain Control Plane (AICP). Recognizing the risks posed by adversarial machine learning attacks, the deliverable analyzes potential threats—particularly black-box evasion and energy-latency attacks—and recommends mitigation strategies such as adversarial training, randomized smoothing, and API security with mutual authentication to safeguard AI models and ensure system integrity.

Formal verification of the proposed security protocols is conducted using symbolic modeling and the Proverif tool, providing high assurance of secrecy, authentication, and integrity properties. Through iterative refinement, vulnerabilities were identified and addressed, ensuring that the PREDICT-6G protocols withstand realistic threat models, including compromised multi-domain entities.

Chapter 4 presents a comprehensive techno-economic analysis contextualizing PREDICT-6G within the emerging 6G ecosystem. It highlights the growing demand for deterministic, reliable, and scalable networks driven by applications in mission-critical communications, smart manufacturing, and multi-domain deterministic services. The analysis discusses the evolving European and global market landscape, emphasizing the necessity for innovative business models aligned with sustainability, digital sovereignty, and regulatory compliance. Through detailed use cases, such as smart manufacturing, the project demonstrates potential capital expenditure (CAPEX) and operational expenditure (OPEX) reductions of up to 46% over five years by employing wireless deterministic technologies and virtualization. The SWOT analysis identifies strengths like technological readiness and modularity, opportunities in shaping standards and emerging markets, and challenges related to integration complexity and device support.

Chapter 5 offers pragmatic migration guidelines for integrating PREDICT-6G into existing telecommunications infrastructures. It advocates a modular, phased integration approach that respects the heterogeneity of current networks comprising 3GPP, TSN, DetNet, Wi-Fi, and more. Key principles include separating domain-specific management services interfacing with native technology APIs and an overarching end-to-end management domain that orchestrates deterministic services across domains. The strategy underscores the importance of cross-domain time synchronization, proposing models for grandmaster clock selection and synchronization relay to uphold stringent timing requirements. For non-deterministic domains, the guidelines suggest embedding extended functions or deploying dedicated edge/cloud-native modules to approximate deterministic behavior. Security is emphasized throughout integration phases, recommending mutual authentication, encryption, and AI/ML security hardening to protect the control and data planes.

In summary, this deliverable encapsulates the technical maturity and readiness of PREDICT-6G's security framework, business viability, and implementation strategy, positioning the project as a significant enabler for the forthcoming 6G era. It offers a blueprint for delivering secure, reliable, and deterministic multi-domain services that meet the stringent requirements of next-generation industrial and mission-critical applications, while providing actionable pathways for adoption and standardization alignment.

2 Introduction

The PREDICT-6G project addresses the emerging need for advanced, secure, and deterministic networking solutions tailored for the evolving landscape of 6G communications. As telecommunications transition from traditional throughput-centric models to services demanding ultra-reliable, low-latency, and predictable performance, PREDICT-6G proposes an innovative framework that integrates multi-technology and multi-domain capabilities. Central to this framework are two key components: the Multi-domain Data Plane (MDP), which ensures deterministic packet forwarding across heterogeneous network domains, and the AI-driven Multi-stakeholder Inter-domain Control Plane (AICP), which orchestrates these capabilities to deliver end-to-end deterministic services. This architecture not only addresses current challenges in interoperability and service automation but also incorporates robust security mechanisms, including inter-domain authentication, integrity and message protection, path redundancy, and the securitization of AI components, to safeguard the network against evolving threats.

The project further substantiates its technical contributions through comprehensive techno-economic analyses, demonstrating the viability and business potential of its solutions, particularly in mission-critical sectors such as smart manufacturing, critical communications, and multi-domain deterministic networking. These analyses reveal substantial reductions in capital and operational expenditures alongside enhanced productivity and flexibility, underpinning PREDICT-6G's value proposition in fostering industrial digitalization and supporting Europe's strategic objectives in 6G leadership and digital sovereignty. Recognizing the heterogeneous nature of existing telecommunications infrastructures, the project outlines a phased migration strategy that emphasizes modular integration, capability assessment, deployment of domain-specific management services, and seamless orchestration with existing operational systems. This approach ensures minimal disruption while enabling the gradual introduction of deterministic networking features.

In summary, this document presents the final specification of the PREDICT-6G architecture, detailing its security framework, economic rationale, and practical guidelines for migration towards 6G scenarios. It encapsulates PREDICT-6G's commitment to delivering a scalable, secure, and efficient deterministic network management solution that aligns technological innovation with business innovation, paving the way for the future of interconnected, intelligent, and resilient communication networks.

3 Final PREDICT-6G Specification

The system architecture of PREDICT-6G was initially sketched in D1.1 and developed with further details in D1.2. Such architecture considers the high-level functional description of the Multi-technology multi-domain Data-Plane (MDP), matter of development in WP2, and the AI-driven Multi-stakeholder Inter-domain Control-Plane (AICP), subject of development in WP3. The low-level details of MDP and AICP have been further described in the corresponding deliverables of WP2 and WP3 respectively.

One aspect of the PREDICT-6G architecture not covered yet in detail in any of the existing deliverables is the one referring to security. Thus, this section details different security concerns of applicability to PREDICT-6G as complementary angle to the system definition. Thus, in the next sub-sections the following topics are discussed:

- Elements to secure PREDICT-6G networks, including Integrity and message protection, and path redundancy.
- Securitization of AI components of PREDICT-6G.
- Verifying security mechanisms.

3.1 Elements to secure PREDICT-6G networks

PREDICT-6G networks will offer a range of security elements to deal with several types of threats as described in D1.1. An example of such an element is considered in **Figure 3-1** below, which depicts the authentication process as part of the End-to-End (E2E) MD. In the same way, other security procedures are part of the E2E MD coordinating domain specific MD.

Figure 3-1: Procedure for sharing keys between two Multi Domains.

3.1.1 Inter-domain authentication

The proposed cross-domain authentication scheme enables the management of domain 1 (MD1) to complete a secure mutual identity authentication when interacting with the MD2. This is considered an inter-domain authentication process that is facilitated by the end-to-end management domain (E2E MD), where the latter accommodates a distributed ledger (DL). Here below in this mechanism, the certificate issue has been already carried out. Moreover, the E2E MD retains a registration authority (RA) and a certificate authority (CA) to manage the authentication process [1][2].

The MD1 has certificate *Cert1*. The specific cross-domain authentication process is explained below. First, MD1 sends a connection request to the MD2 in domain *B*. MD1 queries the authentication information from the MD2_RA server. If the query result is null, the device needs to initiate a cross-domain authentication request. The MD2_RA generates a random number *N* and sends it back to MD1. MD1 signs the number *N* using its private key *SK1* to get $sign(N, SK1)$. Meanwhile, it performs a hash operation on *Cert1* and sends *Cert1*, $Hash(Cert1)$, and $sign(N, SK1)$ to MD2_RA.

MD2_RA starts cross-domain authentication after receiving the above parameters. The authentication process continues as follows.

MD2_RA analyzes certificate *Cert1* to get public key 1 (PK1) and identity information and uses *PK1* verifying the signature to get the random number *N*, then it compares *N* with the generated *N* before. If the result is different, the cross-domain request is refused. Otherwise, MD2_RA initiates a certificate information querying transaction to the blockchain. The transaction

obtains the hash value and the status of the certificate and verifies whether the certificate's status is valid. If it is invalid, the authentication fails. Otherwise, the hash value is compared with the hash value in the request parameter. If it is different, the cross-domain request is rejected. Otherwise, MD2_RA stores certificate of MD1, encrypts the certificate *Cert2* of MD2 with the PK1 and sends it to MD1 to allow access.

Figure 3-2: a) reaching the E2E MD and b) finalizing it through the DL.

The cross-domain authentication of device MD1 to MD2 is completed through the above process. In contrast, the cross-domain authentication process of MD2 to MD1 is similar to the above process, which will not be repeated here.

3.1.2 Integrity protection

One of the main contributions in the proposed solution is the cancellation of the usage of Certification Authority (CA) for issuing and verifying the digital certificates that contain the public key of the requested entity [3]. Instead of using the traditional Public Key Infrastructure (PKI), Pre-shared Key (PSK) is used and implemented to exchange PKs between different parties who wish to communicate. The procedure is explained below while **Figure 3-3** below depicts it as well.

- MD1 asks the E2E DL for the public key PK2 of MD2.
- E2E DL responds with the public key PK2 of MD2.
- MD1 encrypts a Nonce (N1) that uniquely identifies a transaction and the identity of MD1 with the public key of MD2 PK2.
- MD2 asks the E2E DL for the public key PK1 of MD1.
- E2D DL responds with the public key PK1 of MD1.
- MD2 sends to MD1 the already received Nonce (N1) and another Nonce (N2) encrypted with public key PK1 of MD1.
- MD1 re-sends the received Nonce (N2) to MD2 encrypted by PK2.
- A generated Key k_s is signed with the private key of MD1 and the whole message is encrypted with the public key PK2 of MD2.
- MD2 decrypts the message using both private key PK2 of MD2 and verifies the signature using public key K1 of MD1.
- Such session key K_s is shared between MD1 and MD2. This key can be used for setting up any type of secure communication between the end devices and the server.

Figure 3-3: Procedure for sharing keys between two Multi Domains.

Note:

The interesting note of the authentication and integrity protection through blockchain presented above is that the latter can be used for public key exchange for the former instead of PKI for the following reasons:

- Using a PSK instead of PKI in a blockchain protocol is feasible in certain environments, especially where trust is established out-of-band, or the network is permissioned.
 - PSK is simpler and faster for environments where all participants are known ahead of time.
 - Reduces overhead from certificate issuance and revocation.

Pre-Shared Keys (PSK) are particularly well-suited for use in blockchain systems operating within private or consortium settings, where the number of participating nodes is known and limited. In such controlled environments, secure channels can be established in advance for the distribution and management of keys, minimizing the risk associated with key exchange. This approach is especially beneficial for real-time systems where low latency is critical, as PSK-based authentication eliminates the overhead of complex key negotiation protocols.

Overall, PSK offers a lightweight and efficient security mechanism for trusted networks that prioritize speed and simplicity.

Traditional authentication solutions like PKI are often centralized and heavy-weighted, which cannot meet all the requirements of a multi-domain network and thus, we recommend the PSK over PKI.

3.1.3 Message protection

This subsection presents the message authentication code (MAC) system to protect the messages between two management domains that consist of the following three parts:

- A key generation algorithm selects a key from the key space uniformly at random, which has been discussed above.
- A MAC generation algorithm efficiently returns a tag given the key and the message.
- A verifying algorithm efficiently verifies the authenticity of the message given the same key and the tag. That is, return *accepted* when the message and tag are not tampered with or forged, and otherwise return *rejected*.

Figure 3-4: Detailed procedure for sharing keys between two Multi Domains.

MACSec deployment for predictive type of networks may have some implications that we discuss below thoroughly [4]:

- PTP requires message protection to provide reliable, unmodified information.
- MACsec helps to achieve such protection while encrypting the PTP traffic and any other traffic.
- MACsec can provide security guarantees without violating the tight timing constraints.
- There are significant challenges regarding integrating MACsec and with TSN on hardware, as even low data rates already violate the timing constraints posed.
- It does not model many of the real-world aspects of the system, such as CPU/memory usage, memory access, communication access times via the PCI bus, or vendor-specific standard implementation.

Finally, there are significant challenges regarding integrating MACsec and with TSN on hardware, as even low data rates already violate the timing constraints posed [5].

3.1.4 Path redundancy

With the continuous evolution of mobile networks, the development of a **6G architecture** must focus on redundancy, resilience, and intelligent resource management to ensure ultra-reliable and low-latency communications (URLLC). One of the critical areas of enhancement in 6G is the **multi-layer AMF (Access and Mobility Management Function)** redundancy strategy, which ensures high availability and seamless failover mechanisms while optimizing network resources.

In addition to this redundancy approach, we introduce a new component –the **Path Computation Engine (PCE)** [6]– which leverages Graph Theory [7] to enhance network efficiency. This component dynamically determines optimal network paths to minimize congestion, enhance load balancing, and improve fault tolerance. The integration of this intelligent path computation mechanism ensures that the system can precompute and store network paths, making them available upon request, reducing latency and computational overhead and increasing security by offering the possibility to choose an alternative path when one is affected by an attack.

This architecture is proposed for two distinct scenarios:

- **3GPP Classical Architecture** – Standardized 6G architecture based on traditional 3GPP principles.

- **3GPP Enhanced for Deterministic Networking (DetNet)** – A modified approach optimized for ultra-reliable, time-sensitive communication.

The Necessity of Path Redundancy in 6G Networks

Modern wireless networks must support a diverse range of services with varying requirements for latency, bandwidth, and reliability. Given these constraints, a single-layer AMF or a fixed routing mechanism is insufficient for ensuring service continuity, particularly in scenarios involving:

- **Geographically Distributed Networks:** Users move across regions, and a centralized AMF approach may introduce delays and single points of failure.
- **Load Balancing Requirements:** Dynamic traffic fluctuations require a network that can adaptively distribute user sessions to avoid congestion and optimize resource utilization.
- **Failover Mechanisms:** The ability to quickly switch to an alternative AMF or network path is crucial for seamless mobility and uninterrupted communication in case of node failures.
- **Resource Optimization:** Efficient routing helps in reducing power consumption and maximizing network throughput, a key requirement for sustainable 6G networks.

Thus, a **multi-layer AMF redundancy strategy** combined with an **intelligent path computation mechanism** addresses these challenges by **providing proactive failover, optimized routing, and dynamic path allocation**.

Main approach

The proposed 6G architecture introduces a **multi-layer AMF redundancy strategy** to ensure high availability and seamless mobility. The integration of a **Path Computation Engine** based on **Graph Theory** further enhances the resilience and efficiency of the network by **enabling intelligent, proactive routing**. Through **queue theory-based performance evaluation** [8], we aim to validate the effectiveness of this architecture in achieving optimal network reliability, failover handling, and resource optimization.

This hybrid approach—combining redundancy, dynamic path computation, and mathematical performance modelling—lays the foundation for the next-generation self-optimizing 6G network, applicable to both **3GPP classical** and **3GPP enhanced for DetNet** scenarios.

Introduction of the Path Computation Component

The **Path Computation Engine (PCE)** is a newly introduced component designed to enhance network efficiency by intelligently determining optimal network paths. The PCE operates based on Graph Theory, utilizing nodes (network entities like AMFs and UPFs) and edges (communication links) to compute the best possible paths for user sessions. The key functionalities of the PCE include:

- **Data Collection from AMF:** The PCE continuously gathers real-time data regarding network congestion, latency, failure states, and available resources from different AMF instances across geographical locations.
- **Path Computation:** Using **Graph Theory algorithms** [7] such as *Dijkstra's shortest path, A search, or minimum spanning tree algorithms**, the PCE computes the most efficient paths.
- **Path Storage:** Once computed, the paths are stored in a dedicated path repository [9], ensuring that they can be retrieved instantaneously when needed.
- **On-Demand Path Delivery:** Whenever the network requires an updated route (due to a new session request or network failure), the stored paths are provided to minimize latency and optimize traffic flow.

The process of data collection and the process of path computations are asynchronous. The Path delivery mechanism will return the latest path available on the storage (cache) mechanism offered by Redis DB.

By using asynchronous processing, pre-computing paths and storing them for rapid retrieval, the PCE ensures that 6G networks can handle highly dynamic environments with minimal disruptions.

Application in Two Scenarios: Classical 3GPP vs. 3GPP Enhanced for DetNet

The approach is applied in two main scenarios. In the first one a classical 3GPP network is considered while the second one considers a 3GPP network enhanced for DetNet.

3GPP Classical Architecture

Considering a 3GPP classical architecture, the new PCE will be used in the following way:

- The AMF redundancy mechanism ensures load balancing and geographic failover based on classical 3GPP principles.
- The PCE computes paths by considering standard network slicing and mobility patterns.

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- UPF selection remains based on latency, Quality of Service (QoS), and traffic optimization within a best-effort service framework.

There are three components updated or added to the architecture:

- The AMF is changed to:
 - Feed monitoring data, in asynchronous mode, in the new PCE
 - Retrieve the best paths from the PCE
- The p6g-Path, part of PCE, is responsible for:
 - Monitoring data collection from AMF
 - Best independent paths computations
 - Path storage in Redis DB
- Redis DB is memory storage (cache mechanism) where the last best independent computed paths are stored. It is responsible for:
 - Paths storage
 - Paths retrieval and sent to AMF.

The sequence diagram for this case is presented below in **Figure 3-5**.

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Figure 3-5: Path Redundancy Sequence Diagram 3GPP.

In **Figure 3-5**, Step 1, Step 2 and Step 4 are normal, existing steps in a 3GPP Sequence diagram while Step 3 and Step 5 are new introduced steps.

In Step 3, the modified AMF feeds monitoring data, asynchronously, in the newly created entity called **Path Computation Engine (PCE)**. Next, the engine computes the best independent available paths and stores them in the Redis DB (memory cache database).

In Step 5, after UE makes a connection request to AMF, the AMF requires available paths and obtains them from the cache.

Finally, in Step 6, the final connection is established but based on the result of Step 5.

3GPP Enhanced for DetNet

In the 3GPP enhanced for DetNet the approach is like the classical 3GPP, but enhanced to deal with the following characteristics:

- Strict deterministic policies are applied for latency-sensitive traffic.
- The PCE is enhanced with real-time traffic engineering to compute paths with bounded latency and jitter.
- UPF and AMF selection prioritize DetNet-aware network slices, ensuring end-to-end time-sensitive communication for industrial automation, autonomous driving, and critical IoT applications.

There are three components updated or added to the architecture:

- The AMF is changed to:
 - Feed monitoring data, in asynchronous mode, in the new PCE
 - Retrieve the best paths from the PCE
- The p6g-Path, part of PCE, is responsible for:
 - Monitoring data collection from AMF
 - Best independent paths computations
 - Path storage in Redis DB
- Redis DB is memory storage (cache mechanism) where the last best independent computed paths are stored. It is responsible for:
 - Paths storage
 - Paths retrieval and sent to AMF.

The sequence diagram for this case is presented below in **Figure 3-6**.

In **Figure 3-6** Step 1, Step 2, Step 3 and Step 5 are normal, existing steps in a 3GPP DetNet Sequence diagram, while Step 4 and Step 6 are new introduced steps.

In step 4, the modified AMF feeds monitoring data, asynchronously, in the newly created entity called **Path Computation Engine (PCE)**. Next, the engine computes the best independent available paths and stores them in the Redis DB (memory cache database).

In Step 6, after UE makes a connection request to AMF, the AMF requires available paths and obtains them from the cache.

In Step 7, the final connection is established but based on the result of Step 5.

Figure 3-6: Path Redundancy Sequence Diagram 3GPP DetNet

PCE Approach

Path computation is done to check if there are at least two paths from each input node to each output node. There are three main steps performed for path computation on the topology shown in **Figure 3-7**, i.e., any existing cycles are removed, then checks if there are at least two paths between any input nodes and any output nodes are performed, and lastly nodes are sorted by their total weight. This process can be extended to the overall network, so results are obtained for the other nodes.

Figure 3-7: The first three independent paths between two nodes (1 and 9)

Redundant Path Computation

The redundant path computation follows the results obtained by the analysis described in the previous section where finally all the paths were identified. Having these results, two main operations are considered: (1) compute the first 3 shortest paths to define redundancy; and (2) use deterministic algorithms to assign primary, secondary and failover routes, ensuring that no node is left isolated.

The paths used are as follows:

- **Primary Path** - The shortest path typically minimizing latency and optimizing resource utilization, making it ideal for regular traffic.

- **Secondary Path** - The second shortest path providing a backup route that is still efficient, ensuring minimal disruption in case the primary path fails;
- **Failover Path**- The third shortest path providing a tertiary fallback, further increasing fault tolerance.

By explicitly defining primary, secondary, and failover paths, the system can implement deterministic behaviour during failures, ensuring predictable and controlled responses. This design reduces the probability of a complete network outage, thus increasing the availability of the network.

Performance Evaluation Using Queue Theory

To validate the effectiveness of the proposed multi-layer AMF redundancy strategy and Path Computation Engine, we employ **queueing theory** to model and analyze network performance. The evaluation will consider:

- **AMF Load Distribution:** Understanding how well the redundancy strategy distributes users across multiple AMF instances.
- **Path Computation Efficiency:** Measuring the impact of precomputed paths on reducing network latency.
- **Failover Response Time:** Assessing the speed at which sessions are redirected in case of an AMF or UPF failure.
- **Overall Network Throughput:** Quantifying improvements in bandwidth utilization and packet delivery efficiency.

Using **queueing models M/M/C** [10] it is possible to analyze the impact of different redundancy and path computation strategies on network performance. To work with this approach, we must characterize the traffic, based on the monitoring of data registered previously.

Traffic Characterization refers to

- (1) defining arrival rates λ for input nodes and service rates μ for each node in the graph, where the arrival rates will be parameters used when starting the simulation, and
- (2) modelling exponential distributions. Mean service time = 5 is used for the exponential distributions used for service time.

Queue Characteristics include (1) assigning queue discipline FIFO, to each node, and (2) associating latency and jitter effects with queuing delay. **Figure 3-8** shows the queue lengths over trials, providing initial results, without path redundancy.

Figure 3-8: Queue simulations before applying PCE

The previous diagrams will be correlated with the results:

Average Queue Length (L_q): 0.36

Average Time Spent in the System (W): 0.01

Dropped Packets: 5

This is a clear indication that the buffer (queue capacity) is too small, and therefore there are 5 dropped packets. To avoid this, we use PCE to give us the best approach.

Thus, after running again the simulations the result looks like this in **Figure 3-9**:

Figure 3-9: Queue simulations after PCE usage

This is a clear indication that there are no delays or blocking sessions.

Summary of the new proposed architecture

The new proposed architecture, based on the PREDICT-6G one, both with or without DetNet enhancements is represented in **Figure 3-10**.

The left part represents the existing architecture, with all the components and their interactions. On the right part, is the new PCE, which is linked asynchronously with the existing architecture.

The PCE collects data from AMF, then gives back, on request the best paths. The main components of the PCE are:

- **Communication bus.** It is responsible for the communication between the new PCE and the AFM. The communication is asynchronous.
- **Data monitoring and process.** Is responsible for collecting monitoring data from AMF and placing them in the corresponding database.
- **Path computation service** is responsible for:
 - Data representation as graphs

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- Cycle removal
- Independent paths computation
- Selection of best three paths
- Store the paths in the corresponding Precomputed Paths Database cache
- **Path delivery service** is responsible for answering AMF requests for the best paths, by retrieving data from the cache mechanics.
- **Monitoring data** is the database where the configuration data and the real-time monitoring data are stored.
- **Precomputed paths** are a cache mechanism, where the latest computed paths are stored.

Figure 3-10 : New proposed architecture

3.2 Secure AI components in PREDICT-6G networks

One of PREDICT-6G’s main objectives was to develop an AI-driven Multi-stakeholder Inter-domain Control-Plane (AICP). On the one hand, introducing AI in the control plane (CP) causes significant improvements on the capabilities of the control plane for enabling determinism in multi-stakeholder multi-technology 6G environments as it was described in D3.1 and D3.3. However, on the other hand, the application of AI in the PREDICT-6G system also brings in AI related security risks into the PREDICT-6G system. Thus, it is important to investigate the security impact of the application of AI components on the PREDICT-6G system and to propose the right mitigation measures.

This section introduces the results of the analysis on the security and trust impact of AI technology from the PREDICT-6G system point of view. The methodology of the analysis followed the following principles:

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1. Study the potential AI attack and defense mechanisms through the taxonomy and terminology provided by NIST Trustworthy and Responsible AI report [11].
2. Identify the attacks applicable to AI models and MLOps used in PREDICT-6G.
3. Recommend the integration of applicable mitigations.

The NIST report [9] developed a detailed taxonomy and terminology of attacks and mitigations based on the comprehensive review of the Adversarial Machine Learning literature. The document looked at the different lifecycle stages of attack, the attacker's goals and capabilities, and provided the related methods for mitigating the impacts of the attacks. On high-level, two categories of AI classes are defined: (1) Predictive AI (PredAI) and (2) Generative AI (GenAI).

The AI models in the case of PredAI are used for identifying patterns based on historical data and making predictions on future trends and outcomes. In the case of GenAI, the AI models learn the distribution of the data used for training and generate similar samples (e.g., LLMs). It can be concluded that in PREDICT-6G, only PredAI is considered. Therefore, GenAI related attacks and mitigation were not included in the analysis regarding the security impact on PREDICT-6G. However, it should be noted that using the same methodology, the analysis could be extended to GenAI, if (in the future) such models would be considered for PREDICT-6G.

The NIST report [9] identified three different attack objectives, six possible capabilities of the attacker, and mapped the attack types to the identified objectives and capabilities for PredAI systems. These findings are summarized in **Figure 3-11**. The attacker's objective (cf. columns in **Figure 3-11**) can be either to make the AI/ML system unavailable/break down its performance (Availability breakdown) or to provide incorrect output (Integrity violation) or wants to learn information either about the training data or about the AI/ML model (Privacy comprise). As the result of a risk-based analysis considering the impact of the different attack types, it can be concluded that availability breakdown and integrity violation are the most impactful attacks, as they can disrupt the operation of the PREDICT-6G system through degrading the AI model's performance or causing wrong model outputs. Thus, these two types of attack will be further analyzed from the PREDICT-6G point of view.

		Attacker objectives		
		Availability breakdown	Integrity violation	Privacy compromise
Attacker capabilities	Training data control	Data poisoning	Targeted poisoning Backdoor poisoning	
	Source code control		Backdoor poisoning	
	Test data control		Backdoor poisoning Evasion	
	Model control	Model poisoning	Model poisoning	
	Label limit	Clean-label poisoning	Clean-label poisoning Clean-label backdoor	
	Query access	Energy-latency	Black-box evasion	Model extraction Reconstruction Membership inference Property inference

Figure 3-11: Overview of PredAI attacks.

The six capabilities the attacker can have (cf. rows in **Figure 3-11**):

- Training data control: having control over a subset of training data.
- Source code control: modification of the ML algorithm source code.
- Test data control: perturbation of testing samples.
- Model control: control over model parameters.
- Label limit: control over training labels in supervised learning.
- Query access: the attacker can submit queries and obtain predictions.

In a PREDICT-6G system, the most likely attacker capability is the Query access (i.e., access to APIs rather than access to data, models and platforms during the training, or the MLOps framework). Thus, it can be concluded that in case of a PREDICT-6G system, the most impactful attacker objectives are availability breakdown and integrity violation, and the most reasonable attacker capability is the query-access, the attack classes to be analyzed further are Energy-latency and Black-box evasion. However, it should be noted, to mitigate for other attack capabilities, implementations of the PREDICT-6G reference system architecture are advised to adopt state of the art mitigation techniques and standard IT security in order to protect their platforms, data, models and MLOps procedures from adversary impact. E.g., adversary training to protect against poisoning attacks.

In case of the Black-box evasion attack, the attacker’s objective is to compromise the integrity of an ML model’s output, resulting in incorrect predictions performed by an ML model (integrity

violation). The adversary's goal is to generate adversarial examples, which are defined as testing samples whose classification can be changed at deployment time to an arbitrary class of the attacker's choice with only minimal perturbation. To achieve this, the attacker interacts with a trained ML model by querying it on various data samples and obtaining the model's predictions without information about how the model was trained. This can have two subtypes:

- Score based attacks: when attackers obtain the model's confidence scores.
- Decision based attacks: when only the model's prediction is available (more realistic).

There are three major techniques to mitigate the impact of the black-box evasion attack, it is advised the implementation of the PREDICT-6G system use one or more of them:

- Adversarial training (including adversarial samples in the training data).
- Randomized smoothing (train under Gaussian noise perturbation).
- API security with mutual authentication (this was already proposed in D1.2).

In case of the Energy-latency attack, the attacker's objective is to break down the performance of the model at deployment time (availability breakdown). Energy-latency attacks exploit the performance dependency on hardware and model optimizations to negate the effects of hardware optimizations, increase computation latency, increase hardware temperature, and massively increase the amount of energy consumed. E.g., generate adversarial examples that take unusually long time/energy to compute, increasing the latency of the model's response, causing delayed decisions that depend on the model's output. The attacker's capabilities are the same as the black-box evasion attack. There are two major techniques to mitigate the impact of the energy-latency attack, it is advised the implementation of the PREDICT-6G system use one or both:

- Defense strategy to shift the analysis of energy/time consumption from an average-case to a worst-case perspective.
- API security with mutual authentication (this was already proposed in D1.2).

Summarizing the outcome of the work, it can be concluded that the implementation of the PREDICT-6G system should focus on mitigating the impacts of black-box evasion and energy-latency attacks for PredAI. As first line of defense, it is advised to apply API security with mutual authentication to prevent unauthorized access to model APIs. As second line of defense, it is advised to increase the robustness of AI models using (1) defense strategy to shifting the analysis of energy/time consumption from an average-case to a worst-case perspective and (2) randomized smoothing (not model specific, therefore recommended over the model specific adversarial training – yet adv. training can also be done).

3.3 Verifying security mechanisms

Another dimension of the security aspects considered for PREDICT-6G is related to the verification of security mechanisms in the project.

3.3.1 Methodology

The methodology adopted in PREDICT-6G to verify the security mechanisms proposed in the project is based on formal methods. For this reason, after introducing formal methods and their role in security protocol verification, we describe the tools chosen for this purpose in the project and how they can be used to reach the goal.

Introduction to Formal Models, Formal Verification and Formal Methods

Formal models are rigorous and mathematically based models designed to represent IT systems precisely and unambiguously. Common formal models include formalisms like state machines and graphs, which can represent both hardware and software IT systems precisely and unambiguously. Formal verification consists of proving the correctness of formal models used during the development of an IT system, e.g. by proving the correspondence between requirements and their implementation or the correctness of refinement steps.

Formal models and formal verification are collectively known as formal methods. According to Clarke et al [12], formal methods provide a foundation for verifying system correctness and are particularly effective in the context of security-sensitive applications.

In the field of security protocols, formal methods are vital for analyzing the correctness of new security protocols when they are designed to provide high levels of security assurance for them. Indeed, designing a security protocol right is a difficult and error-prone task, because of the multiplicity of the ways a protocol can be attacked, which is difficult to master manually, likely leading to introducing protocol flaws. Instead, by employing formal methods to model and analyze a security protocol, it is possible to find and fix weaknesses so raising its security assurance level.

Approaches to Security Proofs

Security proofs for security protocols can use two kinds of formal models:

- **Symbolic Models:** High-level abstractions that rely on symbolic representations of data and operations. These models are often easier to automate and scale for large systems, but they neglect some aspects of a protocol that could be vulnerable, such as the specific cryptographic algorithms used to implement cryptographic operations and covert channels.

- **Computational Models:** Lower-level approaches that consider cryptographic primitives and their computational hardness assumptions, which are typically more precise but harder to automate.

Verification methods based on symbolic models offer practical advantages because of their simplicity, scalability, ease of automation, in addition to the availability of efficient, stable and reliable tools like *Proverif*. This is why they are the approach most frequently used for analyzing security protocols, despite its inability to find all the weaknesses of a protocol, but only those related to the protocol logic. It is important to note that symbolic models capture the most important type of weaknesses that may affect a security protocol such as man-in-the-middle and replay attacks. For the above reasons, symbolic models have been selected

Key Aspects of Symbolic Modeling

Symbolic modeling, also known as Dolev-Yao [13] modeling, assumes:

- Abstract data types where cryptographic operations are treated ideally (e.g., perfect encryption and decryption).
- Comprehensive attacker capabilities, such as reading, modifying, or injecting messages.
- Inability of the attacker to guess secrets or infer partial knowledge of them.

The goal is to prove that protocols remain secure under these assumptions using automated tools like *Proverif*. The Dolev-Yao model simplifies the representation of cryptographic operations while preserving their essential properties for security analysis.

Proverif for Security Protocol Verification

Proverif [13], developed by Bruno Blanchet, is a state-of-the-art tool for verifying the security of protocols based on symbolic models. Its features include:

- Efficient theorem proving for standard security properties (e.g., secrecy, authentication, integrity).
- Capability to handle infinite state models through modeling of unbounded number of sessions.
- Automated attack reconstruction to provide insights into potential vulnerabilities.

Proverif's resolution-based algorithm ensures rigorous analysis of logical flaws while excluding issues related to cryptographic implementations, quantitative timing, or side channels. Blanchet's work [14] and the abundant related literature demonstrated *Proverif*'s effectiveness in verifying real-world protocols such as TLS and Kerberos and the ability of this

kind of analysis of spotting several types of logical protocol weaknesses. Proverif has also limitations, mostly related to the nature of symbolic modeling. Specifically, in addition to not modeling the details of cryptographic algorithms but only their ideal properties, a relevant limitation of Proverif and other similar tools is their inability to model quantitative time but only event ordering relations. This implies that time-related security properties may be expressed to a limited extent. Despite these limitations, Proverif is useful in improving the quality of the custom protocols designed in the project. Further analyses may be necessary to complement Proverif analysis before a production stage, but this is outside the scope of the project.

Steps for Custom Protocol Verification with Proverif

The verification process for custom protocols based on Proverif that will be used involves the following steps:

Step 1: Security Protocol Threat Modeling

Clearly define the protocol's structure, entities, and operations, taking care to:

- Specify the threat model. In this phase it is necessary to answer questions like “what channels are accessible to an attacker?” or “what knowledge does the attacker have initially?” or “are there protocol entities that may be compromised?”.
- Address ambiguous protocol details, ensuring all relevant scenarios are considered.

Step 2: Security Property Elicitation

Security properties define the guarantees the protocol must uphold, such as:

- **Secrecy:** Ensuring sensitive data remains confidential.
- **Authentication:** Verifying the identity of entities involved.
- **Integrity:** Guaranteeing that certain data are not tampered with during transmission.
- **Replay Resistance:** Preventing attackers from reusing old messages to interfere with the normal protocol behavior, e.g. impersonating legitimate parties.
- **Non-repudiation:** Ensuring that entities cannot deny their actions within the protocol.
- **Availability:** Guaranteeing that the protocol remains operational even under certain types of attacks.
- **Forward Secrecy:** Ensuring that compromise of long-term keys does not expose past session keys or communications.

In this step, the security properties relevant for the protocol are identified.

Step 3: Formal Specification and Verification by means of Proverif

Formalize the protocol behavior, assumptions and properties and express them in the language accepted by Proverif. Then, run the tool to get the verification results. More precisely:

1. **Formalizing the protocol:** Representing the protocol's roles, operations, communication channels, and participant behaviors in Proverif's language. To check that the protocol behavior has been formalized correctly, it is recommended to include a number of sanity checks that Proverif has to verify in the formal verification stage.
2. **Encoding security properties:** Translating the defined properties into logical queries for Proverif to verify.
3. **Running verification:** Executing Proverif to check for potential attacks or violations of the specified properties.

Step 4: Iterative Refinement

Based on Proverif's results, it may be necessary to refine the protocol and property models iteratively. For example:

- Correct the protocol model if sanity checks fail.
- Address any detected vulnerabilities by checking whether they are real true positives or false positives.
- If a detected vulnerability is a false positive originating from modeling errors on the protocol or on the properties or assumptions, refine the Proverif model accordingly.
- Based on the results obtained, reevaluate assumptions about the attacker's capabilities.

This iterative process aligns with principles of secure development as outlined by Anderson [15].

Challenges and Limitations

While the defined methodology based on symbolic verification and Proverif offers significant advantages, it has certain limitations:

- **Idealized Cryptographic Assumptions:** Real-world cryptographic flaws, such as side-channel attacks, or the possibility of brute-force attacks based on weaknesses of the specific cryptographic algorithms selected for the protocol are not modeled.

- **Scalability:** For highly complex protocols, the symbolic representation might become computationally intensive. However, for the protocols defined so far the complexity is manageable as it will be shown in the section about verification examples.
- **Tool-Specific Constraints:** Each tool, including Proverif, has limitations in terms of expressiveness and the types of properties it can verify.
- **Time-Related Aspects:** Symbolic models often assume instantaneous operations, neglecting time delays or synchronization issues that could be exploited by attackers. For instance, protocols vulnerable to timing attacks may require additional modeling layers or real-time analysis techniques to address such vulnerabilities effectively.

3.3.2 Verification example

In order to illustrate the methodology presented in the previous section more concretely, we present an example of application to one of the protocols proposed so far, i.e. the protocol illustrated in **Figure 3-3**.

The purpose of this protocol is to allow the cancellation of the usage of Certification Authority (CA) for issuing and verifying the digital certificates that contain the public key of the requested entity [3], using Pre-shared Key to exchange PKs between different parties who wish to communicate, providing cross-domain authentication.

Step 1: Security Protocol Threat Modeling

The actors of this protocol are the Multi-Domains (MD) that need to establish mutual authentication and key exchange (MD1 and MD2 in the picture) and the end-to-end Distributed Ledger (E2E DL in the picture) where the public keys are stored and made available.

The protocol behavior and procedure we will consider is the one described in section 3.1.2.

As a threat model, in this example we assume the E2E DL is contacted by MD_i via secure channels, while we assume the communications between two different MD_i transit across insecure channels. For what concerns the possibility that entities are compromised, we assume this applies only to multi domains and not to the E2E DL and we evaluate two different scenarios: (1) No MD is compromised; (2) One MD has been compromised, so being untrusted.

We assume the attacker may access the E2E DL to get the public keys and corresponding MD identities

Step 2: Security Property Elicitation

We consider the following security properties:

1. Secrecy of the session key K_s established through the protocol and data encrypted with it.
2. Mutual authentication of MD1 to MD2 and MD2 to MD1 and their agreement about the established session key

Other properties could be defined, but for simplicity we limit our analysis to these two properties only.

Step 3: Formal Specification and Verification by means of Proverif

The protocol roles and exchanged messages can be described in Proverif language as shown in **Figure 3-12** (initiator, MD1) and **Figure 3-13** (responder, MD2). It must be noted that a typo in the figure was corrected: ID2 in the first message should be ID1.

As the DL is assumed to be connected to the MD i via a secure channel, the interaction with the DL is represented simply by a function $d//$ that maps an identifier to the corresponding public key.

Sanity checks have been added to ensure each protocol role can reach its end of session.

```
(* Process that represents the MD that starts the protocol *)
(* id1 is the initiator identity, kp1 its key material, id2 the responder
identity *)
let p1(id1:bitstring, kp1: keymat, id2:bitstring) =
let pk2:pkey = dl(id2) in (* get pk2 from the DL *)
new n1:bitstring; (* generate nonce n1 *)
out(c,penc((id1,n1),pk2)); (* send message Encrypt pk2 {id1, n1} *)
in(c,x:bitstring); (* receive response message x *)
let (=n1,xn2:bitstring)=pdec(x,sk(kp1)) in (* decrypt x with SK1, check it
includes n1 and second nonce xn2 *)
event b1(id1,id2,n1,xn2); (* state session has been started between id1 and
id2 with nonces n1 and xn2 *)
out(c,penc(xn2,pk2)); (* send message Encrypt pk2 {xn2} *)
new ks: bitstring; (* generate session key ks *)
event b2(id1,id2,ks,s); (* state session has been started between id1 and
id2 with ks and secret s *)
out(c,penc((sign(ks,sk(kp1)),xn2),pk2)); (* send message Encrypt pk2 {Sign
sk1{ks}, xn2} *)
out(c,senc(s,ks)); (* secret s is sent encrypted with ks - represents use of
ks *)
event end1(); (* end of session *)
0.
```

Figure 3-12: Proverif description of initiator MD.

```

(* Process that represents the MD that responds *)
(* id2 is the responder identity, kp2 its key material *)
let p2(id2:bitstring, kp2: keymat) =
in(c,x:bitstring); (* get first message x *)
let (id1:bitstring,xn1:bitstring)=pdec(x,sk(kp2)) in (* decrypt x with sk2
and extract id1 and xn1 *)
let pk1:pkey = dl(id1) in (* get PK1 from the DL *)
new n2: bitstring; (* generate nonce n2 *)
out(c, penc((xn1,n2),pk1)); (* send message Encrypt pk1 {xn1,n2} *)
in(c,y:bitstring); (* get response message *)
let (=n2)=pdec(y,sk(kp2)) in (* decrypt response and check it contains n2 *)
in(c,z:bitstring); (* get next message z *)
let (xks:bitstring,=n2)=pdec(z,sk(kp2)) in (* decrypt z with sk2 and check
it contains signature xks and n2 *)
if checksign(xks, pk1)=ok() then (* check signature xks with pk1 *)
let xks:bitstring=getmess(xks) in (* extract session key xks from signature
*)
event e1(id1,id2,xn1,n2); (* state session has been completed between id1
and id2 with nonces xn1, n2 *)
in(c,w:bitstring); (* get encrypted session message w *)
let xs:bitstring = sdec(w,xks) in (* decrypt w with xks and get secret xs *)
event e2(id1,id2,xks,xs); (* state session has been completed between id1
and id2 with xks and xs *)
event end2(); (* end of session *)
0.

```

Figure 3-13: Proverif description of responder MD.

The security properties can be formalized as:

1. Secrecy of the session key K_s established through the protocol and data encrypted with it.

query attacker(s).

2. Authentication of MD1 to MD2 and their agreement about the established session key

event b1(bitstring,bitstring,bitstring,bitstring).

event e1(bitstring,bitstring,bitstring,bitstring).

query z:bitstring, w:bitstring; event(e1(MD1,MD2,z,w)) ==> event(b1(MD1,MD2,z,w)).

Property 2 means that whenever event $e1(MD1,MD2,z,w)$ occurs, i.e., whenever MD2 states a session with MD1 has finished with nonces z and w , event $b1(MD1,MD2,z,w)$ occurred in the past, i.e. MD1 stated a session with MD2 with the same nonces z and w . In this way we are guaranteeing authentication and agreement on the nonces.

When Proverif runs with the hypothesis that no MD is compromised, all properties are proved to hold. If instead we assume one MD is compromised, Proverif finds an attack on the protocol that, after checking, can be classified as a true positive.

The attack works as shown in **Figure 3-14**.

Figure 3-14: Attack found by Proverif verification.

In the attack scenario, MD1 starts a session of the protocol with the compromised MD3 which itself starts a session with MD2 pretending to be MD1 and replaying the same $n1$ received from MD1. MD2 responds according to the protocol. MD3 cannot decrypt this message but can forward it to MD1. This is a valid response to the first message issued by MD1. Hence, MD1 confirms it has started a valid session with MD3 (event $b1(MD1,MD3,n1,n2)$) and proceeds according to the protocol by sending the last two messages to MD3, completing the session. MD3 can decrypt these messages and get $n2$ and ks from them. Moreover, MD3 can successfully complete the protocol session with MD2. At the end, MD2 has been tricked into believing it has completed a session with MD1 (event $e1(MD1,MD2,n1,n2)$) while in fact this is not true, because MD1 did not intend to start a session with MD2. From this point on, MD3 can continue the interaction with MD2 using the session key ks which it knows, pretending to be MD1 (and MD2 will believe it is interacting with MD1 while in fact it is interacting with MD3).

Step 4: Iterative Refinement

Under the assumption that MD can be compromised or not trusted, the proposed protocol can be attacked. For this reason, it must be fixed and formal verification has to be repeated on the fixed version.

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The protocol can be fixed by adding the responder's identity in the second message of the protocol, which becomes Encrypt PK1 {ID2,N1,N2}.

The fixed version of the protocol has been formally verified, and Proverif proved all the properties on it successfully.

3.3.3 Second Verification example

As a second example, we consider the protocol for inter-domain authentication illustrated in **Figure 3-2**.

The purpose of this protocol is to perform a cross-domain authentication between two multi domains (MD1 and MD2).

Step 1: Security Protocol Threat Modeling

The actors of this protocol are the Multi-Domains (MD) that need to establish mutual authentication (MD1 and MD2 in the picture) and the E2E MD that includes the Registration authority and Certification authority of MD2 (MD2_RA and MD2_CA in the picture) and the end-to-end Distributed Ledger (E2E DL in the picture) where the public keys are stored and made available.

The protocol behavior and procedure we will consider is the one described in section 3.1.1, **Figure 3-2 (b)**.

However, after discussion with the proposers, it was clarified that this protocol also requires the protocol of section 3.1.2 **Figure 3-3** to run successfully. If the latter does not run or fails, the multi-domain authentication fails as well. More precisely, this run of the protocol shown in **Figure 3-3** should involve MD2 and MD1. Moreover, it has been clarified that in this protocol the actors shown as MD1 and MD2 in Figure 3 are to be interpreted as the CAs of MD1 and MD2, i.e. MD1_CA and MD2_CA.

In this example we use a threat model like the one illustrated in the previous section, i.e., we assume the E2E DL is contacted by MDi_CA via secure channels, while we assume the communications between two different MDi transit across insecure channels. We also assume the communications inside a MD (e.g., between MDi_RA and MDi_CA) occur on secure channels. For what concerns the possibility that entities are compromised, we make the same assumptions made in the previous example, i.e., we assume only multi domains may be compromised and not the E2E DL and we evaluate two different scenarios: (1) No MD is compromised; (2) One MD has been compromised, so being untrusted.

We also assume the attacker may access the E2E DL to get the public keys and corresponding MD identities

Step 2: Security Property Elicitation

We consider the following security properties:

1. Mutual authentication of MD1 to MD2 and MD2 to MD1 and their agreement about the MD2 certificate

Other properties could be defined, but for simplicity we limit our analysis to this property only.

Step 3: Formal Specification and Verification by means of Proverif

The protocol roles and exchanged messages can be described in Proverif language as shown in **Figure 3-15** (MD1, sending the access request) and **Figure 3-16** (MD2-RA and MD2-CA, handling the request). The formal description has been obtained from the description in section 3.1.1 and **Figure 3-2**, after having obtained some clarifications about their interpretation. Specifically, about the last step of the protocol, written “Sign Cert2 with PK1” in the picture, it was clarified that the right meaning is the one in the text, i.e. “MD2_RA stores certificate of MD1, encrypts the certificate *Cert2* of MD2 with the PK1 and sends it to MD1 to allow access”, which corresponds to sending the message `Encrypt PK1 {Cert2}`.

In this protocol, MD1 contacts the MD2_RA, while the MD2_CA acts as a simple forwarding agent for messages to/from the E2E DL. As we are assuming that communications between MD2_RA and MD2_CA happen through a secure channel, the two entities are merged into a single Proverif process (MD2-RACA). Moreover, as in the previous example, the DL is assumed to be connected to the MDi_CA via a secure channel, thus the interaction with the DL to obtain Cert info is represented simply by a function `getcercert` that maps an identifier (e.g., MD2) to the corresponding digital certificate (e.g., *Cert2*).

As with the previous protocol, sanity checks have been added to verify that each protocol role can reach its end of session.

The successful completion of the protocol means that MD1 has obtained the certificate of MD2 (*Cert2*). The public key contained in this certificate is used to encrypt a secret, *s2*, which must not be accessible to the attacker. This last step is outside the original protocol, but it has been added just to get one more correctness property, i.e. the secrecy of the exchanged secret *s2*. In this way, if the certificate accepted by MD1 is not *Cert2* but a certificate provided by an attacker, the secrecy of *s2* does not hold.

```
(* Process that represents the MD that starts the protocol *)
let md1(id1:bitstring, kp1: keymat, id2:bitstring) =
  (* MD1 starts the process in Fig. 2 *)
  out(c, (id1, id2, access_req)); (* MD1 starts auth process to get access to MD2 *)
  in(c, nonce:bitstring); (* response from E2E-MD *)
  let sign1 = sign(nonce, sk(kp1)) in (* sign the nonce *)
  let cert1 = getcert(id1) in (* get certificate *)
  event beginMD(id1, nonce, pk(kp1));
  out(c, (sign1, cert1)); (* send response with signed nonce *)

  in(c, enccert2:bitstring); (* receive response with encrypted MD2 cert *)
  let cert2 = btoc(pdec(enccert2, sk(kp1))) in (* decrypt cert2 using sk1 *)
  event endMD(cert2, nonce);

  out(c, penc(s2, getpk(cert2)));
  0
.
```

Figure 3-15: Proverif description of the MD process sending the access request.

```
let md2ca(id2:bitstring, kp2ca: keymat, id1:bitstring, s:bitstring) =
  (* MD2-CA starts the process in Fig. 312 *)
  (* ... *)
  (* --- End of process in Fig. 312 --- *)

  in(c, (mdx:bitstring, mdy:bitstring, = access_req)); (* receive request from mdx to access mdy *)
  if mdx = id1 then (* id authorised since it has completed the previous phase *)
    new nonce:bitstring; (* generate nonce *)
    event beginMDCA(mdy, mdx, nonce);
    out(c, nonce); (* send nonce *)
    in(c, (signx:bitstring, certx:certype)); (* receive response with signed nonce *)

    if checksign(signx, getpk(certx)) = ok() then (* verify signature *)
      if getmess(signx) = nonce then (* verify nonce *)
        if certx = getcert(mdx) then (* verify validity of the certificate *)

          event endMDCA(mdx, nonce, getpk(certx));
          let enccerty = penc(ctob(getcert(mdy)), getpk(certx)) in (* encrypt certy with pkx *)
          out(c, enccerty);

  0
.
```

Figure 3-16: Proverif description of the MDi-RACA handling the request.

The security properties can be formalized as:

1. Secrecy of s_2 encrypted using the public key contained in the certificate obtained from MD2-RACA at the end of the protocol.

query attacker(s_2).

2. Authentication of MD1 to MD2-RACA

event beginMD(bitstring, bitstring, pkey).

event endMDCA(bitstring, bitstring, pkey).

query n:bitstring, k:pkey; event(endMDCA(MD1, n, k)) ==> event(beginMD(MD1, nonce, k)).

3. Authentication of MD2-RACA to MD1

event endMD(certtype, bitstring).

event beginMDCA(bitstring, bitstring, bitstring).

query n:bitstring; event(endMD(getcert(MD2), n)) ==> event(beginMDCA(MD1, MD2, n)).

Property 2 means that whenever event $\text{endMDCA}(\text{MD1}, n, k)$ occurs, i.e., whenever MD2-RACA states it has completed a session with MD1 having public key k exchanging the nonce n , then event $\text{beginMD}(\text{MD1}, \text{nonce}, k)$ occurred in the past, i.e. MD1 started a session with MD2-RACA with the same nonce and key. In this way we are guaranteeing authentication of MD1 to MD2-RACA.

Property 3 means that whenever event $\text{endMD}(\text{getcert}(\text{MD2}), n)$ occurs, i.e., whenever MD1 states it has received the certificate of MD2 from the MD2-RACA during a session using nonce n , event $\text{beginMDCA}(\text{MD1}, \text{MD2}, n)$ occurred in the past, i.e. MD2-RACA started a session with MD1 requesting the certificate of MD2 using nonce n . In this way we are guaranteeing authentication of MD2-RACA to MD1 and the integrity of the received certificate.

After running Proverif, we found that only property 2 holds in the protocol while properties 1 and 3 do not, and this is regardless of the presence/absence of compromised MDs. In

particular, Proverif found that there is no authentication of MD2-RACA in all its messages to MD1. The attacks on the protocol found by Proverif is shown in **Figure 3-17**.

Figure 3-17: Attack found by Proverif verification.

Step 4: Iterative Refinement

The proposed protocol can be attacked as shown in the previous step. For this reason, it has to be fixed, and formal verification must be repeated on the fixed version.

Looking at the attack, it is due to the lack of a proof of authenticity in the last protocol message. Encryption with MD1’s public key is not enough. A signature done with MD2’s secret key is necessary to prove the authenticity of the message origin to MD1.

The fix consists of including a signature in the message from MD2_RA to MD1 containing the encrypted MD2’s certificate. More precisely, the signed message becomes $\text{Sign}(\text{Encrypt}_{PK1}(\text{Cert2}, N, MD1))$. The signature must also cover the nonce (N) exchanged at the beginning of the protocol and the identifier of the recipient (MD1), to prevent the attacker from bypassing the protection by simply replaying a different certificate signed by MD2_RA, exchanged in a previous session between MD1 and MD2_RA itself.

With this fix, even property 2 holds, as it has been confirmed by running Proverif on the fixed version of the protocol.

3.4 Conclusion

This chapter has covered in depth different security aspects related to the PREDICT-6G architecture to provide protection, robustness and operational verification. The security framework for the PREDICT-6G architecture should address (among other potential aspects) integrity and message protection across all communication layers, ensure path redundancy to maintain resilience against failures or attacks, incorporate securitization measures for AI components to prevent misuse or compromise, and include mechanisms for continuous verification and validation of all implemented security controls.

4 Techno-economic analysis and business dimension of the project

The current very early stages of 6G standardization and pre-development activities pose important challenges to conduct a techno-economic analysis of the main exploitable results of PREDICT-6G. Whilst the technological advancements of 6G have garnered significant attention and the need for innovative business models is widely anticipated, the economic viability of solutions that have not yet been properly developed nor consistently integrated in the overall telecommunication system remain largely unaddressed. This general lack of data has a substantial impact on the development of technoeconomic analysis, which can only rely on assumptions and largely forecast.

The deployment and operation of the future 6G network is expected to result in substantial infrastructure investments. Therefore, the transition from 5G to 6G requires a careful planning of the interplay between several factors such as anticipated technology enablers, applications, services, business models, and regulations to ensure the affordability of 6G system.

We have opted to follow the 6G Technoeconomic Framework (6G TEF) developed by [16] to perform a techno-economic analysis of the main project results. The 6G TEF considers the interplay between technological advancements, investment costs, revenue models, and market dynamics. It aims to facilitate a comprehensive evaluation of the costs, benefits, and potential risks associated with the successful and sustainable deployment and operation of 6G networks.

These recommendations include clarifying QoS assumptions, utilizing meaningful financial metrics to reflect increased network virtualization, quantifying uncertainties in the 6G model through sensitivity analysis, openly sharing 6G model data and code, and promoting greater collaboration between economists and engineers. This highlights the need for comprehensive

techno-economic analysis to assess the feasibility and viability of 6G networks from both technical and financial perspectives.

4.1 The advent of 6G: an overview

The world is becoming increasingly interconnected and reliant on digital technologies, with wireless communication playing a pivotal role in transforming economic, production, and social models.

While the deployment of the 5th generation of wireless technologies (5G) progresses, the next generation, 6G, is expected to offer a more advanced and comprehensive user experience achieving a greater optimisation of the performance and efficiency of telecommunications [17], fuelled by the demand of business and consumers for advanced network solutions that meet the stringent requirements of data-intensive applications and emerging technologies [18].

Augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), extended reality (xR), pervasive Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), holographic communications, big data, cloud/edge computing, blockchain and distributed sensing are some of the emerging technologies that require communication networks that can ensure determinism, predictability and reliability. Such networks are expected to deliver consistent enhancements to several system KPIs and to include advanced features at both the control and data planes, among which traffic prioritisation, forwarding or replication capabilities, and flexible management interfaces (API).

The technological transformations driven by 5G are also reflected in new ecosystem dynamics, characterised by an increased interdependency and collaboration among diverse actors - operators, technology providers, application developers, etc. - that need to continuously adapt and evolve in response to technological advancements, market demands, and regulatory changes.

The telecommunications sector has evolved from linear value chains to complex value networks [19]. In this context, each actor delivers only a part of the solution, removing the need to own or operate all components.

Business models need to account for this relationship between ecosystems and value networks characterised by a growing **interdependency** between actors, the **dynamism of interactions** and the **co-creation of value**, which entails that multiple stakeholders contribute with their expertise and resources to formulate, build and deliver innovative solutions. Likewise, aligning the business models with the sustainability principles, integrating them in the value networks, is essential for a supporting the social objectives.

6G is expected to help bridge the digital divide that is progressively growing. Remote areas, developing countries and rural communities need to be offered connections to high-speed

Internet to be able to access advanced digital services like remote education and healthcare, and other government services. This would expand the 6G market as well as contribute to socio-economic development, generating more economic opportunities and digital inclusion on a global scale.

Figure 4-1: Plethora of traditional and new services, across multiple domains [19]

4.1.1 The European Union and 6G

The European Union (EU) has a long-standing commitment to enhancing connectivity for the benefit of its people. Yet, the limited uptake of digital technologies constrains innovation, new services and consequently, EU productivity and global competitiveness. The advent of 6G is expected to accomplish a true Digital Single Market (DSM), unlocking new business models and driving growth across strategic sectors such as services, energy, defence. [20].

Investments in the next wave of frontier technologies, in particular supercomputing, new materials, AI at the edge, genomics, and quantum computing, are crucial due to their expected impact in the communication technologies. Of particular interest are also technologies enabling low latency and reliable delivery of information. Moreover, a safer, more trustworthy AI, a key EU priority, will underpin these advances enhancing system predictability and responsiveness across domains.

To achieve a truly digital society, the EU has established a set of key priorities and strategic directions, namely: foster joint activities, partnerships and vertical industries engagement; work towards a cohesive European voice; leverage 5G lessons to align tech advancements with market needs; define Key Value Impact (KVI) indicators for positive societal impact; and, ensure full alignment with EU policies and priorities.

It is also important to mention the emphasis that the EU places on standardisation, as a critical pillar of the DSM and thus, the competitiveness of the European industry [21].

4.1.2 The PREDICT-6G business case

Current networks struggle to meet the performance requirements needed to support mission-critical, time-sensitive, and high-reliability applications. Traditional networks are best-effort and cannot guarantee a consistent performance. They operate with high latency, limited interoperability and still rely on manual processes in the absence of automation and built-in intelligence.

PREDICT-6G has redefined the networking paradigm by proposing some technology enablers and a network and management framework that allow a secure, interoperable, time-sensitive and scalable deterministic network. The proposed framework automates the definition, provisioning, monitoring, fulfilment, and life-cycle management of E2E deterministic services over multiple network domains.

The concept is grounded in three core pillars:

- **Enhanced reliability and time sensitive features** of IEEE 802.11 and 3GPP networks, including APIs for the monitoring and control of such capabilities, enabling predictability even in environments lacking native deterministic capabilities.
- A **multi-technology multi-domain Data-Plane (MDP)** jointly with an **AI-driven multi-stakeholder inter-domain Control-Plane (AICP)**, combining IETF DetNet and RAW mechanisms for creating E2E deterministic paths.
- **New AI methods and Digital Twins (DTs)** to enhance the predictability of the network, forecast the use of resources, and assess the impact of new traffic.

PREDICT-6G has followed a four-step approach to deliver the proposed framework, **Figure 4-2**.

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Figure 4-2: PREDICT-6G approach

PREDICT-6G offers a robust and future-ready solution to the current challenges in deterministic networks. It addresses critical limitations by ensuring predictable, low-latency, and highly reliable connectivity whilst enabling seamless integration across diverse technologies and multiple domains, including 3GPP, TSN, DetNet, and Wi-Fi.

The proposed network architecture is flexible, scalable, interoperable, secure and adaptable. Leveraging intelligent automation, it enables E2E service provisioning, monitoring, and lifecycle management, significantly reducing operational complexity, human errors and overhead while improving performance and resource efficiency.

Built with AI and DT technologies, the framework anticipates network conditions and proactively addresses potential issues, ensuring optimal service continuity. It can be tailored to diverse industry needs and scenarios while embedded security mechanisms safeguard the data and infrastructure from cyber threats. Furthermore, it has been developed in alignment with industry standards and current regulation to support regulatory compliance from the outset.

The project value proposition is relevant to many sectors that involve deterministic communications and services. Meeting the stringent performance demands of emerging application and supporting future 6G integration and evolving network advancements, it will maintain a long-term competitive edge.

The business model of PREDICT-6G consider different revenue streams, including commercial agreements with third parties and subscription fees. It is noteworthy that the open-source approach of the project ensures its core framework remains accessible to a wide range of organisations. Ultimately, PREDICT-6G aims to provide a novel deterministic architecture for beyond 5G and 6G applications to foster innovation, strengthen Europe’s competitiveness, and contribute to the broader digitisation of the industry.

4.1.3 PREDICT-6G Stakeholders

PREDICT-6G can offer benefits to a wide range of stakeholders. More specifically, application sectors and the players in the overall 6G ecosystem are expected to gain the most from the PREDICT-6G proposal,

Figure 4-3: PREDICT-6G stakeholders

4.1.4 Innovation Items, Key Exploitable Results and Technology Readiness Levels

PREDICT-6G identified seven expected Key Exploitable Results (KERs) in the description of action (DoA), compiled more than three years ago at project proposal submission phase. Those KERs have all been successfully worked on along the project lifetime, through a set of parallel smaller activities called ‘innovation items’, each one related to an advance of the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of some aspects of the to-be 6G network. More details on the process, part of the innovation program of the project, that allowed the identification of those innovation items can be found in D5.4. More details on the innovation items themselves can be found in WP2 and WP3 final deliverables D2.4 and D3.4.

TRLs compose a scale used to assess the maturity of a technology, ranging from basic research to full-scale deployment. It helps to provide a common understanding of the development stage of a technology and its potential for commercialisation. The TRL scale consists of nine levels, each representing a specific milestone in the technology development process. The

lower levels (TRL 1-3) focus on basic research and proof of concept, while the higher levels (TRL 4-9) involve development, testing, and deployment.

The KERs can be mapped to the mentioned three main PREDICT-6G innovations, as shown in **Figure 4-4**. It is worth noting that MDP and AICP can be also considered building blocks of an advanced architecture for 6G. And that the innovation pertaining to the Novel Architecture for 6G are a set of items that considered instrumental for an effective integration of MDP and AICP into a future 6G architecture.

Figure 4-4: PREDICT-6G KERs as defined in the DoA mapped into key innovations

The set of innovation items can be mapped to the KERs as shown in **Table 4-1**, which also shows the end TRL of each one of them. It is worth noting that there is some overlap of innovation items and KERs, i.e., one innovation item can be mapped to more than one KER. That is because it is very hard, if possible, at all, to completely de-couple the control and data planes (AICP and MDP) activities in a research project.

Most innovation items have reached a TRL4 at the end of the project, thanks to their integration into the use cases defined by PREDICT-6G in manufacturing and communications. Of those, the following five are anticipated to be further developed, tested and validated until ready for commercialisation (for more details one can refer to the partner-specific exploitation plans described in D5.4).

- TSN software switch
- TSN on Wi-Fi
- TSN on 3GPP networks
- Advance data monitoring and KPI prediction
- DT Models for TSN KPI estimation

Table 4-1: KERs, Innovation Items and end TRLs

KER		Innovation items	TRL
Novel Architecture for 6G			
MDP	Enhance determinism at selected L2 technologies // Integrate different L2 technologies, from different domains into a single E2E data- plane	TSN software switch	TRL 4
		TSN on Wi-Fi	TRL 4
		TSN on 3GPP networks	TRL 4
	Enhance determinism at selected L2 technologies	Dynamic scheduling	TRL 3
	Expose control APIs to enable CP to configure determinism // Integrate different L2 technologies from different domains into a single E2E data- plane	DetNet-based MDP	TRL 4
		How to handle determinism in a non-deterministic network	TRL4
AICP	AI-based network CP framework // Monitoring platforms for deterministic networks	Zero-touch control for deterministic E2E services / set of components of AICP	TRL4
		Secure AI model transfer within 3GPP	TRL4
		Management of zero deterministic networks	TRL4
	Network DT	DT Models for TSN KPI estimation	TRL4
	AI-based network CP framework	AI-based resource allocation	TRL3
	Monitoring platforms for deterministic networks	Secure AI model transfer within 3GPP	TRL4
AICP & MDP	Expose control APIs to enable CP to configure determinism // Network DT	Advance data monitoring and KPI prediction	TRL4

In terms of commercial exploitation of the main project results, licensing to Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEMs) and companies seems to be the most promising path. A **software license** could provide legal access and usage rights to a solution based on PREDICT-6G. The licensing agreement could be perpetual, subscription-based (e.g., monthly or yearly) or pay-per-use. The services would include the monitoring and management of the software

license compliance as well as support for upgrades as per the license terms. Licensing the **Intellectual Property** (IP) derived from the project innovations would allow the legal use or exploitation of assets such as patents, copyrights, or trademarks. This would facilitate technology transfer and/or partnerships.

Additional options to be explored are partnerships and alliances, data and analytics and consulting services.

- **Partnerships and alliances:** revenue from strategic partnerships and collaborations. For instance, the PREDICT-6G solution could enter the market via an integrator that becomes responsible to provide the turnkey solution. The revenue is then shared amongst the various owners/vendors of the different components in accordance to a pre-established agreement.
- **Data and analytics:** revenue from providing analytics and insights derived from the data.
- **Consulting Services:** revenue from deployment, integration, customisation, and consulting services related to the P6G solution.

PREDICT-6G prioritises responsible management and IP protection while fostering open-source collaboration and knowledge sharing by adhering to the principle that results generated within the project belong to the beneficiary who created them. Jointly developed results with inseparable parts are jointly owned unless agreed otherwise. Access rights to background knowledge are granted royalty-free for project execution, and specific rules regarding IP, results, and background are defined in the Grant Agreement.

4.2 6G market forecasts

The global 6G market was valued at USD 5.1 billion in 2023 and it is expected to grow at CAGR of 34.2% from 2023 to 2030. The revenue is forecasted to reach USD 40.2 billion in 2030 driven by the increasing demand for high-speed, ultra-low latency, seamless connectivity and the progressive adoption of advanced technologies [22]. BIS Research estimates that the market will grow at a 103,35% from 2029 to 2035 and reach \$1,293.19 billion by 2035¹.

The 6G market is in its early stages of development but the application areas are ever growing. Envisioned to provide unprecedented data rates, ultra-low latency, ubiquitous connectivity, and enhanced reliability, 6G is also riddle with challenges that might impact its widespread adoption. The deployment and scalability of the infrastructure requires substantial investments and proper logistical and technical solutions. Moreover, the elaboration of

¹ Note: the market projections for 6G vary across sources

appropriate standards and protocols and the establishment of data protection regulations are highly complex.

The propagation of connected devices and the rise of data-driven applications call for robust security and privacy measures. The development of encryption protocols and secure authentication mechanisms is therefore another focus area, where quantum communication might be key. Effective data governance frameworks that guarantee transparency, accountability and user content in handling confidential information are crucial.

All these elements might hinder the transition from 5G and – in some cases even older communication generations – to 6G. Addressing these challenges necessitates a holistic approach that considers both the technical capabilities and economic viability of the network.

Governments are heavily funding 6G R&D as well as in infrastructure to promote the adoption of 5G. Likewise, the private sector is investing in R&D of advanced solutions for the 6G network capabilities. Collaboration among stakeholders, from both the public and private sectors, is a priority.

The advent of 6G is anticipated to enable novel business models. Harnessing its potential can boost efficiency and productivity. It also can unlock innovation, opening new avenues for breakthrough applications and services, disrupt industries, and overall create high added value for business and consumers and favour economic growth.

Currently, North America holds the largest share of the 6G market followed by Europe. However, Asia is the fastest growing 6G market with countries like China offering strong government support and Japan and South Korea being at the forefront of 6G innovation, with their major telecommunication companies actively investing in next-generation networks and services [23].

It is also important to consider the social, economic and environmental context in the development of 6G. Sustainability is one of the main 6G drivers in terms of technology design to minimise its own environmental footprint and as an enabler to reduce the carbon footprint. Security, trust and privacy as well as ethical considerations are also central to 6G advancement. Lastly, geopolitical concerns should not be underestimated as shown by the impact of the semiconductor scarcity, the digital divide and the emphasis on technological sovereignty.

4.2.1 6G market drivers, trends and sectors

6G will change the telecommunications landscape powering the industry digitisation. A wide range of technologies and applications are anticipated to tap into the network advanced capabilities to fulfil its potential, which in some cases was hindered due to the 5G limitations.

The evolution of service delivery models that begun in the 5G era, triggered by two technology-driven trends, could also benefit from the 6G capabilities. The first trend relates to the industry transformation required to overcome cost inefficiencies and low flexibility in delivering new 5G services, namely: enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), ultra-reliable low latency communications (URLLC) and massive IoT (mIoT). The second trend pertains to a technological paradigm shift towards full softwarisation of network functions and network architecture disaggregation thereof [24].

The dependency on technology and communication networks demands a high-quality service. Recent advancements have enabled to use interactive applications such as multiplayer online gaming, videoconferencing, live streaming and financial trading applications, which require rapid processing, queuing, serialisation, and network transfer of signals.

The responsiveness of these specific applications directly impacts the user experience. In some cases, interruptions and lag might even endanger people and cause important economic losses [17]. Thus, services providers are working to minimise network delay to meet the growing demand for low latency network for specific applications (including the variability of such latency, or jitter).

The transition to 6G occurs in a context of substantial changes in telecommunications that pose important challenges but also offer opportunities. The fragmentation of the Internet has become a reality with profound effects in interoperability. The introduction of varying technologies and regulations have splinted the “centralised Internet” into different ones, i.e., the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in the European Union or the Chinese government control.

Building infrastructure closer to costumers that allows more control, and lower latency is gaining traction. Similarly, the network architecture is experiencing demands that often require finding a balance between contradictory needs: open access versus controlled safety, centralisation versus decentralisation, or networks-as-a-service and AI-optimised networks.

A NGMN study identified four trends based on the analysis of 50 use cases “describing forecasted costumer behaviour and demand”, namely: Enhanced Human Communication – like immersive experience; Enhanced Machine Communication – such as interacting cobots; Enabling Services – such as healthcare, smart industry, DTs or positioning; and, Network Evolution – such as trusted native AI and energy efficiency [25]. There are important overlaps and interdependencies among the categories, which in turn are rather comprehensive. The trends are further detailed hereafter.

Applications

The key applications predicted to drive the 6G market include AI, IoT, multisensory extended reality, autonomous and robotic systems, blockchain and distributed sensing and communications [17].

Data-driven technologies such as AI, ML, big data analytics, and cloud computing are becoming widespread across vertical sectors. These technologies rely on massive datasets for training algorithms, making real-time decisions, and extracting actionable insights. Moreover, the adoption of AI and IoT-based communication devices across industries such as smart cities, healthcare, transport or manufacturing, has also gained significant momentum. However, the low data speed rates affect their ability to generate, process and interpret data, leading to delayed response times. 6G is poised to address these issues enabling constant connectivity and the transfer of large volumes of data through IoT devices at a higher speed, easing real-time data processing and analysis and overall enhancing the efficiency of peer-to-peer connections [17].

Multi-sensory XR dominated the market in 2023 [23]. XR, which encompasses technologies such as VR, AR and MR, offers varying levels of immersion and interaction. Aiming to improve the user experience, the integration of all sensory modalities is emphasised, for example, adding tactile and olfactory sensations [26]. Holographic technology will also be relevant in remote collaboration, education, and entertainment.

The Internet of Everything (IoE), defined as the connection of people, process, data, and things through the Internet infrastructure, is also promising [27]. These applications will leverage 6G's capabilities for ultra-low latency, high-speed data transfer, and seamless connectivity to create transformative user experiences.

Lastly, the distributed sensing and joint communications sector is projected to account for the largest market share by 2030 driven by the demand in autonomous systems, smart infrastructure, industrial automation, and critical applications requiring real-time, ultra-reliable connectivity.

Vertical sectors

6G will have an unprecedented impact on multiple vertical sectors.

Manufacturing holds the largest share of the emerging 6G market and is anticipated to continue to do so in the next years as it fulfils the industry 5.0 vision. The integration of 6G technology is expected to enable next-generation production strategies through advanced automation, connectivity, and seamless data exchange. This will enhance manufacturing efficiency, reduce downtime, and support the implementation of advanced technologies such

D1.3 – Final PREDICT-6G specification, techno-economic analysis, and guidelines for migrating to 6G scenarios

as AI, AR, robotics and edge computing. The machine-to-machine (M2M) communication will also open new opportunities, for example, wireless communications in the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), and other edge computing devices.

The automotive industry will benefit from 6G through advancements in autonomous driving, vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication, traffic management and superior safety features. Similarly, 6G will transform healthcare enabling ultra-reliable low-latency communication for telemedicine, remote surgery, real-time patient monitoring, and AI-driven diagnostics. Media and entertainment will experience an in-depth transformation with the integration of fully-fledged immersive experiences. According to SNS OPS D1.2, it is one of the verticals expected to be most impacted by 6G.

Education (e.g., remote and interactive learning), transport and logistics, smart cities (e.g., traffic management, urban planning, energy conservation, resource management), agriculture and public safety, are also noteworthy.

Infrastructure: communication systems and devices

Communication system infrastructures are often divided into fixed and wireless. The advent of 6G will realise the main objective of wireless communications of delivering ubiquitous connectivity, in other words, “systems capable of seamlessly using satellite, cellular, and local area networks to maintain a fast, secure, and reliable online connection” [28]. Among other elements, this requires device compliance with standard protocols and device interoperability, as well as multidomain (5G/6G, Wi-Fi, satellite...) integration. In 2023, the wireless segment accounted for 80% of the revenue share [23].

In terms of devices, smartphones lead the global market and will continue to drive the demand. Tablets, wearables and other IoT devices will gain an important market share thanks to 6G high-speed and reliable connectivity that will allow instant access to content and services anytime, anywhere.

4.2.2 Business models for 6G

The advent of 6G will shift how network resources, data and services are generated, delivered and consumed. This transformation will affect how an organisation creates, delivers and captures value, disrupting traditional business models and ecosystems, unlocking new revenue streams and value-creation opportunities [30].

Literature discussion on 6G business models is very limited. Notwithstanding, studies show an evolution from linear value chains to value networks, where stakeholders interact, exchanging data, services or innovation, to co-create value. Value networks are more flexible

and responsive, better reflecting the dynamism of the 6G ecosystem, as represented in **Figure 4-5**.

Figure 4-5: Value network components in 6G

In this respect, the recognition of 6G as a General-Purpose Technology (GPT) is critical. As a GPT, 6G will drive continuous technological advancements while nurturing cross-sector innovation and industrial complementarities. Understanding the dynamics and interdependencies of these ecosystems will be essential to full harness 6G's potential.

However, the pursuit of viable business models is not straightforward. The transformative nature of 6G requires a holistic perspective, integrating technological, economic and societal perspectives. In fact, the future of 6G telecommunications will be shaped by growing societal requirements like resilience, inclusivity, empowerment, transparency and sustainability. In particular, the EU advocates for an E2E approach – from design to deployment and after end of life - to sustainability in 6G. The regulatory environment also needs to be factored.

4.2.3 PESTEL analysis

The PESTEL analysis is a strategic tool used to assess an organisation's external environment. It examines six key factors: Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal. Considering these factors, organisations can identify opportunities and threats and develop strategies to adapt to the changing landscape. With the PESTEL analysis, PREDICT-6G

gained a comprehensive understanding of the external environment and developed strategies to thrive in the next-generation technologies.

Political

- **EU and 6G:** PREDICT-6G contributes to the SNS JU mission to foster Europe's technology sovereignty in 6G by implementing the related R&I and to boost 5G deployment throughout Europe by developing digital lead markets and enabling the digital and green transition of the economy and society.
- **Government Initiatives:** governments are heavily funding 6G R&D and investing in infrastructure to promote the adoption of 5G, creating opportunities for PREDICT-6G to collaborate with public authorities.
- **Cooperation agreements:** the EU, via the SNS JU, has established several collaboration agreements with third countries, including South Korea or United States. PREDICT-6G could leverage these to expand its reach into new markets.
- **Data Protection Regulations:** Stringent data protection regulations, such as GDPR, will require PREDICT-6G to ensure the highest compliance when dealing with data.
- **Government intervention:** governments may intervene in the 6G market as it is a critical technology for countries' sovereignty, especially in this unstable geopolitical scenario, potentially impacting PREDICT-6G business model.

Economical

- **Growing 6G market:** the global 6G market is growing rapidly, creating significant opportunities for PREDICT-6G to capitalise on the increasing demand for high-speed, ultra-low latency, ubiquitous connectivity, and enhanced reliability across industries.
- **Increased Investment:** the private sector is investing heavily in advanced solutions for the 6G network capabilities, creating opportunities for PREDICT-6G to sell its solution for deterministic networks.
- **Deterministic networks:** the ability to guarantee ultra-reliable, low-latency, and time-sensitive communication, supporting applications across industries, creates many opportunities for PREDICT-6G to explore innovative business models.
- **Competition:** PREDICT-6G faces competition from established players in the provision of determinism, making it necessary to provide a unique value that differentiates its offer and thus, build a strong market position.

- **Monetisation:** 5G has proven difficult to monetise despite its potential due to unclear value propositions, insufficient differentiation from existing services, and high costs and complexity, which may affect the adoption of PREDICT-6G.

Social

- **Growing dependence on reliable connectivity:** society increasingly relies on digital services, demanding ultra-reliable, low-latency, and secure communication. PREDICT-6G can meet these needs.
- **Impact on work and education:** as remote and hybrid work and learning become mainstream, PREDICT-6G can ensure connectivity.
- **Trustworthiness:** concerns around data privacy, security and algorithmic bias shall be addressed by PREDICT-6G to foster adoption.
- **Workforce and skills:** PREDICT-6G can leverage its expertise to train the professionals responsible for operating the solution.
- **Ethical implications:** AI and automation may rise ethical questions in safety-critical application, demanding human oversight, which PREDICT-6G needs to consider.
- **Digital inclusion and accessibility:** PREDICT-6G, if scalable, can bridge connectivity gaps for rural, remote and aging populations promoting equity of access and enabling broader participation in the digital economy.

Technological

- **Interoperability challenges:** the technological fragmentation across network layers (L2/L3), domains (cloud, edge, enterprise) and enabling technologies (TSN, DetNet), requires PREDICT-6G to ensure seamless interoperability.
- **Standardisation:** standardisation in many areas concerning PREDICT-6G architecture is still evolving, which may slow down its deployment.
- **Lack of device support:** DetNet has not been commercialised yet, TSN solutions are not widely adopted, and few network devices and user equipment (UEs) currently support deterministic networking, which may hinder the implementation of PREDICT-6G solution.
- **Security by design:** the increasing sophistication of cyberattacks poses a significant threat, which PREDICT-6G addresses by providing embedded security that supports zero-trust networking models.

- **Resilience:** as applications become more distributed, PREDICT-6G offers a resilient architecture against variable traffic flows and failures and guarantees real-time coordination of demands.

Environmental

- **Growing demand sustainable solutions:** PREDICT-6G offers an optimal allocation of resources that enables an efficient use of power and can reduce energy consumption.
- **Green design principles:** PREDICT-6G can contribute to sustainability by leveraging opportunities to incorporate green practices in its design and operation.
- **Environmental impact:** PREDICT-6G architecture is deployed on top of existing infrastructure, limiting its environmental impact. Moreover, it may enable advanced environmental monitoring systems.
- **Industrial transformation:** the green transition creates opportunities for PREDICT-6G by enabling diverse industries achieve lower emissions, better resource management, and waste reduction
- **Green policies:** governments are regulating emissions and energy use whilst offering incentives to adopt green technologies, which could benefit PREDICT-6G thanks to its ability to optimise resources.

Legal

- **Intellectual Property Protection:** Strong intellectual property protection can help PREDICT-6G safeguard its innovations and compete effectively in the market.
- **Data Privacy Regulations:** Evolving data privacy regulations, such as GDPR, as well as auditability and access control, require PREDICT-6G to ensure compliance.
- **Service Level Agreements (SLAs) and liability:** PREDICT-6G must clearly define responsibilities, remedies, and liabilities in case of non-compliance with performance metrics such as latency or jitter.
- **Cybersecurity Laws:** cybersecurity laws can impose strict requirements on PREDICT-6G, requiring it to invest in robust security measures.
- **AI and automation governance:** emerging legal frameworks tackling AI-driven orchestration and decision-making may affect PREDICT-6G deployment.

4.2.4 Market Gap

Even though there are deterministic solutions available, these are often hindered by integration challenges. Thus, there are many opportunities for PREDICT-6G's novel E2E architecture.

- **Under-served segments:** Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are often under-served by large players, presenting an opportunity for tailored solutions.
- **Industry-specific solutions:** industry-specific solutions are needed to cater to the unique needs of specific industries, such as manufacturing, communications, energy, transport, public safety or healthcare.
- **Absence of automation and intelligence:** manual configuration, monitoring and troubleshooting tends to be slower and more error-prone due to the difficulty to forecast performance, manage resources, and adapt in real time.
- **Emerging applications:** the lack of support to applications such as AR or industrial robotics demand strict performance that current networks cannot deliver.
- **Limited interoperability:** current networks cannot deliver reliable and predictable E2E performance across multiple domains nor technologies opening an opportunity for PREDICT-6G.
- **Unreliable communication:** packet loss, intermittent connectivity or delays can have severe consequences in sectors such as manufacturing or healthcare or simply provide a poor user experience in streaming or gaming.
- **Lack of scalability:** today's deterministic networking is often confined to small, local deployments (e.g., factory floors, private 5G) due to complexity and cost. A scalable architecture that supports broad deployment would fill a critical demand.
- **Insufficient security:** many networks lack built-in, verifiable security creating strong demand for networks that embed zero-trust principles, secure provisioning, and real-time threat visibility.
- **Lack of SLA enforcement tools:** operators often lack tools for real-time visibility, SLA tracking, and performance assurance in deterministic environments, creating an operational gap.

4.2.5 Business opportunities and market position

The market gap analysis identified several areas where PREDICT-6G can provide a valuable solution to address unmet needs in the current telecommunications landscape. Building on

these insights, this section outlines the key opportunities for PREDICT-6G to capitalise on and position itself as a leading provider of deterministic network architecture for 6G.

Mission-critical industries

PREDICT-6G can enable deterministic connectivity for smart factories, smart grids, autonomous vehicles or healthcare, where ultra-reliable, low-latency communications are crucial. These sectors have a high willingness to invest in technologies that guarantee performance and safety.

- **Smart manufacturing**

Deterministic communications are expected to enhance productivity, efficiency, and innovation in smart manufacturing, particularly in areas such as precision manufacturing, real-time control systems and predictive maintenance.

Some of the operations in the manufacturing process are programmed in a sequence that cannot experience any delay nor deviation. PREDICT-6G guarantees an optimal performance across sequential manufacturing processes, minimising the risk of failure and maintaining seamless production continuity.

The integration of mobile and collaborative robots (cobots) in industrial plants, working alongside human workers, has become common. The provision of a wireless deterministic network enables to mitigate current operational risks related to the latency, jitter, and network instability while supporting safe and efficient operations

PREDICT-6G can also improve quality control and supports flexible, scalable production that can give a significant competitive advantage to manufacturers. It also can integrate with existing legacy systems, allowing for a seamless integration and interoperability across domains and reducing the need for investment. Furthermore, PREDICT-6G supports sustainable manufacturing practices by optimising resource use and minimising waste and enables energy efficiency usage.

Private 5/6 networks

Enterprises are deploying private mobile networks to meet specific latency, reliability, and security requirements. PREDICT-6G offers a valuable solution in this space by delivering deterministic network management across multi-domain, heterogeneous environments, especially for Industry 4.0, logistics, and energy.

Network-as-a-Service (NaaS)

PREDICT-6G can provide the foundational architecture to automate definition, provisioning, monitoring, and lifecycle management of deterministic services with guaranteed KPIs.

Cross-Domain Orchestration for Multi-Cloud and Edge

Cloud-to-edge applications (e.g., AR/VR, connected drones, smart mobility) require end-to-end service orchestration across domains. PREDICT-6G can capture value by enabling interoperable, deterministic service paths that span telco, edge, and cloud infrastructures.

Smart Infrastructure and public sector

Governments are investing in resilient digital infrastructure. PREDICT-6G aligns with policy objectives such as technological sovereignty, secure-by-design architectures, and green digital transformation, making it attractive for public-sector deployments in smart cities, utilities, and defence. Public deterministic infrastructure can support a great variety of services.

Standardisation Leadership and First-Mover Advantage

By aligning with emerging standards (e.g., IETF DetNet, IEEE TSN, 3GPP, ETSI), PREDICT-6G can position itself as a reference architecture in the pre-standardisation phase of 6G, influencing specifications and securing early partnerships with key ecosystem players.

Green and Sustainable Networking

Energy-aware orchestration and resource optimisation enabled by deterministic networking support the move toward green ICT and net-zero targets. PREDICT-6G can address enterprise and government demands for sustainable, performance-assured network infrastructure.

Figure 4-6: PREDICT-6G market position

4.2.6 SWOT analysis

The SWOT analysis is a valuable tool for understanding the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats on a given subject. PREDICT-6G conducted a SWOT analysis to gain a clarity on its current position in the market. This analysis will help the project team leverage its strengths, address its weaknesses, capitalise on opportunities, and mitigate threats.

A first consultation was carried out during the Plenary Meeting held in October 2024 in Budapest. The results were then fine-tuned during the Plenary Meeting held in January 2025 in Madrid. This second plenary took place in parallel with the Integration Week, where the team worked to integrate and test the technical advances in the 5TONIC facilities. This timeline also contributed to the maturity of the results included in the SWOT.

Figure 4-7 showcase the results of the SWOT analysis:

Figure 4-7: SWOT analysis

Strengths

Wireless deterministic services across domains, flexibility and automation

PREDICT-6G provides a unique platform that simplifies the management of deterministic services ensuring a reliable, time-sensitive communication across multi-domain networks, handling mixed traffic types. Moreover, the modular and scalable architecture with E2E automated management for deterministic services, guarantees efficiency and adaptability.

Cutting-edge solutions and technology readiness

Even though the project targets medium TRLs, the P6G solution is being built in alignment with Deterministic Networking (DetNet) standards, facilitating its deployment. It also addresses high-precision and low-latency requirements for critical applications such as industrial automation and real-time communications. Furthermore, the integration of determinism with AI-driven Control and Prediction (AICP), surpasses existing solutions. Overall, these advantages make the P6G innovations a very attractive solution to meet the demands of many emerging markets.

Industry & Academic Collaboration

The close cooperation between industry leaders and renowned academic institutions has been an essential element to the success of the P6G ambitions. The team brought together highly skilled experts to solve pressuring technical challenges for the further digitalisation of the industry, driving innovation and expanding the potential of wireless deterministic networks.

Weaknesses

Difficult integration across domains and resource constraints

Ensuring seamless integration across different network domains remains a challenge. Moreover, deterministic networking limits resources available for other services, requiring careful network planning to balance performance and efficiency.

Lack of adoption and device support

DetNet has not been commercialised yet and TSN solutions are not widely adopted. Besides, few network devices and user equipment (UEs) currently support deterministic networking.

Opportunities

Shaping industry standards

PREDICT-6G has actively contributed to standardisation efforts in various areas, in particular, time sensitive networks (TSN), AI-driven Control Plane (AICP) and Multistakeholder Control

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Plane (MCP). This work is the basis to ensure interoperability and industry adoption so that determinism becomes a core feature of next-generation communication systems.

Network design

P6G has laid the foundations to continue developing the next-generation deterministic service management framework that seamlessly integrates DTs and Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) for real-time optimisation. This work paves the way for more intelligent, automated, and resilient network architectures.

Feasibility, real-world impact and emerging markets

The P6G solution showcases the viability of wireless determinism in a wide range of use cases, including mission-critical communications, industrial automation or sensing. The demonstrations, illustrating the potential of deterministic networking in real-world implementations, are strategic to build industry confidence and driving adoption.

As the demand for these capabilities grows across industries and applications, could position P6G as a key enabler for industrial digitalisation, tapping into emerging markets and attracting private investment. Ultimately, this would accelerate its widespread adoption.

Threats

Standardisation, software and hardware limitations

The pace of standardisation for all the deterministic networking capabilities may slow down its availability. There is also a limited availability of standardised interfaces.

There are some hardware limitations related to its incompatibility with user equipment, which may hinder the deployment and testing of determinist networks.

Uncertain market demand

The demand for wireless deterministic networks may still be low, which would require to raise awareness among industry with use cases.

Gap between experiments and real-world conditions

Deviation from actual network conditions in experimental setups may impact performance validation and practical feasibility assessments.

4.3 Particularisation of the analysis for PREDICT-6G use cases

PREDICT-6G has developed three different use cases to test its solution. Two of these cases focus on communications: "**Deterministic services for critical communications**" and

“Multi-domain deterministic communication”, while the third focuses on communications in **“Smart Manufacturing”**.

Each case was analysed to understand the economic value and exploitation pathways potential, contributing to the project's innovation management and long-term impact strategy. The insights gained will support the identification of viable business opportunities and inform future actions toward standardisation, dissemination, and market uptake.

4.3.1 Deterministic services for critical communications

The PREDICT-6G Critical Communication use case addresses the challenge of delivering reliable, time-sensitive, and predictable E2E communication for critical industrial, manufacturing and other applications in operational technology (OT). These applications are expected to meet specific business-level targets, including key performance indicators (KPIs) and key value indicators (KVI).

To achieve this, the underlying network and infrastructure technology must support and, wherever possible, enhance the required performance levels. Consequently, there is a direct and critical link between the technical capabilities of the OT stack and the business-level performance of the solutions and facilities that rely on it.

The aim of PREDICT-6G critical services is to provide a potential boost to the achievable business targets by enhancing or stabilising the network serving the critical communication demand in various OT use cases. However, it is important to note that network level measurable KPIs such as achievable latency, jitter or availability and reliability of the deterministic packet flows, do not necessarily translate to proportional gains in selected business level targets.

In general, a more reliable network helps achieve specific business level targets in a repeatable and dependable manner. However, the quantification of any gains, for example, the monetisation of the improved technological capabilities through business level outcomes, depends on the use case as well as on factors such as specific operational context and the scalability potential of the business solutions involved.

For example, improvements in deterministic networking could increase production volume (e.g., enabling faster and more reliable automated quality control). However, materialising these gains would also require scaling the OT components of the production pipeline, such as increasing the number of Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) for faster material handling or expanding input material sourcing. Given that PREDICT-6G operates at TRL4, a quantitative business-level analysis is not performed for this use case. Instead, we adopt a qualitative approach, identifying key opportunities where enhanced network technology could potentially enable or drive business-level improvements.

The core technology behind the Critical Communication use case is the ability to improve the level of determinism in existing deployed industrial networks, for example a private factory network, through the aftermarket installation of specific data-plane agents that provide over-the-top deterministic packet processing and flow management.

The data-plane agents, referred to as MDP Agents, can be deployed at the Layer-3 (IP) across various network segment, such as 3GPP/5G, Wi-Fi, or fixed IP access. This technology-agnostic approach enables the scalability of the MDP Agent solution for existing businesses, which already have their network infrastructure, allowing them to improve the current network capabilities without further additional CAPEX spending.

As the MDP Agent is a software-based solution, it does not require the purchase of dedicated hardware components. Yet, its deployment on an existing platform requires that the necessary extra packet processing compute capacity is available (or can be obtained) and that the necessary network configuration and integration (e.g., to route the traffic through the deployment points of the MDP Agents) can be performed by the technical staff of the facility hosting the industrial network. Alternatively, deploying the MDP Agent and making the necessary configuration and integration could also be offered as a service by an industrial network operator.

Considering the flexibility of the MDP Agent technology, its integration into an existing network may yield the following potential benefits (this list is not exhaustive, and actual benefits may vary depending on local conditions at each OT facility):

Faster production due to speeding up the operations in the facility

Some networked physical production components may include a safety headroom in terms of execution speed, velocity of movement, or frequency of operations preventing network inaccuracies from causing unsafe conditions, costly errors, or delays.

For example, the speed of a manufacturing tool or a conveyor belt may be limited to ensure reliable operation despite a certain level of packet loss between the controller and the tool. Deterministic networking can eliminate such losses, enabling faster production. Similarly, AGVs may operate at limited speed to avoid collisions caused by delayed network-based guidance. With lower network delay, the AGVs may move faster, increasing throughput in the logistic or material handling. In a third example, deterministic communication can reduce machining failures, such as drilling errors, by ensuring precise control, leading to higher throughput and cost savings.

Improved security in the facility.

Deterministic networks can guarantee that manufacturing control processes detect unsafe or invalid conditions more quickly and reliably whilst delivering faster counteractions. For example, detecting human presence at an unsafe location through video stream analysis may trigger the halting of an automated vehicle or manufacturing tool before the harm occurs. The lower the latency and higher the reliability of the network that provides situational awareness to the control system, the faster the decisions and actions safeguarding the facility.

Enable to use more advanced, efficient (but also more sensitive) equipment

Deterministic networks can enable the integration of highly advanced operational technology (i.e., more autonomous, faster, more complex machining tools) that transform the productivity of the business. While acquiring these new tools requires CAPEX investment, the improvement on the network may be executed without replacing the existing infrastructure, aside from the integration of the MDP Agents as discussed above.

4.3.2 Multi-domain deterministic communication

The PREDICT-6G Multi-Domain Deterministic Communication use case addresses the challenge of delivering reliable, time-sensitive, and predictable E2E communication across heterogeneous network domains. These domains span diverse technologies, including 3GPP, TSN, IETF DetNet, and Wi-Fi, as well as different administrative boundaries.

The core technological concept and component enabling such use case is the MDP, which supports deterministic forwarding through mechanisms like traffic replication, scheduling, and domain border gateways that bridge otherwise disjointed technologies. It is complemented by an AI-driven Inter-Domain Control Plane (AICP), which automates the orchestration, monitoring, and assurance of deterministic services. Time synchronisation, service lifecycle management, and real-time path computation are also integral to the architecture, ensuring strict performance guarantees. By enabling predictable and resilient communication across complex, multi-vendor environments, this approach not only industrial automation and critical communications, but also lays the foundation for future 6G-standardised deterministic networking.

This analysis the potential business viability of an MDP and AICP solution for enabling Multi-Domain Deterministic Communications is assessed. It begins with a SWOT analysis, followed by the identification of major potential choices for articulating a viable business model using the widely adopted Business Model Canvas.

Figure 4-8: Multi-domain deterministic communication use case SWOT

Strengths

The architected solution concept presents major strengths rooted in its advanced technical capabilities. One of its core advantages is seamless interoperability across heterogeneous network domains, including 3GPP, TSN, DetNet, and Wi-Fi, which enables broad applicability in diverse deployment scenarios. It also supports strict E2E requirements for latency, jitter, and reliability, critical for use cases such as industrial automation and remote control. The integration of an AICP adds further value by enabling intelligent orchestration and service lifecycle management across multiple domains. Moreover, the solution incorporates resilient

mechanisms, such as packet replication, to enhance fault tolerance and ensure service continuity.

Weaknesses

The major weakness of the proposed MDP solution lies in the considerable deployment complexity due to the need to harmonise diverse technologies and administrative domains. Such complexity introduces potential challenges to technical scalability, as managing service guarantees across a growing number of domains can strain system performance.

Furthermore, gaps in standardization, particularly within IETF DetNet and 3GPP, pose integration and interoperability hurdles, which also limit or slow initial market uptake and the scalability and sustainability of a business model around this concept. One key gap identified is the lack of handling Detnet service labels within 3GPP networks. Also, it would be critical to standardise TSN features in IEEE 802.11, which is currently not in the SDO roadmap. The initial deployment also demands significant investment in both infrastructure and expertise, raising the barrier for adoption, especially among smaller operators or enterprises.

Opportunities

This solution concept is well-positioned to support emerging 6G applications and Industry 5.0, which demand ultra-reliable and low-latency communication in increasingly automated and data-intensive environments. Its cross-domain capabilities make it broadly applicable beyond telecommunications, extending to sectors such as manufacturing, healthcare, transportation, and critical infrastructure. There is also significant potential for the architecture to shape and influence international standards in deterministic networking. From a business perspective, the platform could be commercialised as a modular orchestration and assurance solution, opening opportunities for licensing, integration services, and long-term support contracts.

Threats

The primary threats to the success of this use case stem from the evolving competitive landscape and potential interoperability issues. Proprietary solutions from major vendors might offer simpler, more vertically integrated alternatives that could be favoured by industry stakeholders seeking quicker deployment. In addition, managing communication across heterogeneous domains introduces security risks and creates new vectors for attack, which may be difficult to control without strict safeguards. Regulatory and data sovereignty constraints could also limit the viability of inter-domain orchestration in certain jurisdictions, slowing adoption and complicating operational models.

Figure 4-9: Canvas model for the Multi-domain deterministic communication use case

Value Proposition

The MDP and AICP solution offers a flexible, software-based framework that enables predictable, low-latency and resilient communication across multiple technological and administrative domains, without requiring the replacement of existing infrastructure. A wide range of heterogeneous infrastructure setups, including TSN-enabled switches, 5G networks, and Wi-Fi domains is considered and supported.

The solution can be tailored to specific critical applications' demands, empowering industries such as manufacturing or critical communications, to upgrade existing networks, ensuring E2E performance. MNOs and neutral infrastructure providers can also pursue this business opportunity, creating a robust business model like the one pitched here for supporting them in this endeavour.

This approach unlocks CAPEX efficiency, accelerates digital transformation, and lays the groundwork for future 6G-standardised deterministic networking, helping businesses stay ahead of evolving technological and operational demands.

Customer Segments

Industry 5.0 leading firms demanding strict latency, jitter, and reliability constraints for safety-critical or real-time control processes spanning across multiple technology domains.

Key Activities

- **R&D activities** encompassing upscaling to production-level the AICP and MDP components. Securing support for SLA agreements for the orchestration of different domains, including data plane connectivity with guarantees and the deployment of DetNet routers in key inter-connection points.

Achieving compliance with industry standards and enabling certification for deployment in regulated environments are critical for supporting sensitive applications like AGV control and time-critical factory operations.

- **Solution Architecture and Delivery**
 - Build out best expertise in serving very heterogeneous types of target environments and specific customer needs, with the same core product portfolio
 - Implement two-way communication and active feedback loops with engaged customers, in order to effectively steer the evolution/roadmap of the portfolio.
- Pre-Sales and Sales activities, for building out a strong B2B channel
- Establish key partnerships with world-class technology providers (see Key Partnerships) and alliances with strategic customers and channels (see Channels).

Key Resources

- Skilled workforce to carry out the underlined key activities of R&D, Solution Architecture, Pre-Sales & Sales, and Partnering.
- Infrastructures for developing, integrating, testing, evolving and maintaining the solution.
- IPR for freedom of development, operation, and commercialization.
- Key Hardware and Software components like:
 - Device-Side and Network-Side Translators (DS-TT/NW-TT), which enable deterministic behavior across technologies.

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- TSN-capable switches, XDP/DPDK-enhanced NICs for programmable data planes, Wi-Fi infrastructure with specific TSN enhancements, UEs, and edge micro data centers.

AICP components such as Service Automation, Measurement Management Services, and Path Computation Elements (PCEs) form the operational core. Domain APIs ensure interoperability across heterogeneous network slices and components.

Key Partnerships

The business model relies heavily on a strategic network of partnerships that includes leading technology vendors such as Ericsson, Nokia, and Intel, who provide essential hardware, protocol stacks, and interoperability support.

Ecosystem-wise, collaboration with standardization bodies like IETF, IEEE, and 3GPP ensures that the solution evolves in line with emerging frameworks for deterministic networking, time-sensitive communication, and orchestration APIs.

Additionally, alliances with industrial associations enable the platform to align with sector-specific compliance, automation trends, and adoption roadmaps, particularly in manufacturing and logistics.

Finally, vertical-specific system integrators are expected to become key partners enriching the channel towards engaged customers.

Customer Relationships

Customer engagement is built on long-term service agreements that guarantee not only technical support but also strategic alignment as needs evolve.

The solution will be deployed via co-creation models, where integration is tailored to specific environments or operational flows, such as DTs or time-sensitive robotic control.

SLA-based models provide both performance accountability and adaptive service layering, aligning closely with the predictive and monitoring capabilities defined in the project.

Channels

The primary go-to-market strategy leverages enterprise pre-sales and account teams within the telco operators, who act as prime contractors for complex deployments.

Direct B2B sales channels support engagements in highly customized industrial contexts. Channels are reinforced through participation in vertical-specific integrator ecosystems that align telco-grade service delivery with operational technology (OT) systems.

Cost Structure

The proposed business model is articulated around both sustained development and integrative activities (with moderate to high CAPEX and OPEX dedicated to R&D, infrastructures, licenses, ...) and the delivery of tailored complex customers solutions, with this high Cost of Sales (CoS).

Focusing on the latter, a key ambition should be to, over time, factor out (mutualise) CoS drivers across customer projects for scaling in revenues and margins in a sustainable way. The very high CoS of initial engagements (at the start of the learning curve for supplying this solution) is a major risk for solution take-off that cannot be under-estimated.

Revenue Streams

We foresee revenue will be generated through a mix of recurring and usage-based models. These include deterministic network subscriptions and overage fees for excess deterministic traffic, for operators. Additional streams come from premium SLAs that include green metrics or sustainability reporting. Incentive-aligned contracts with uptime-based bonuses or penalties align with outcome-driven business models.

Further down in the value chain, for integrators and vendors, revenues will come from new features in hardware or software which will result in increase of prices or extra licensing. One-time revenues include installation and integration services, as well as bespoke proof-of-concept deployments or DT simulations billed on a time-and-material basis.

Techno-economic analysis

Focusing on the viability of solution adoption, the business incentives were analysed for a concrete potential adopter of the MDP solution.

The MDP solution may be applied to different scenarios, therefore its techno-economic analysis highly depends on the specific scenario. To provide one example on how the application of the MDP concept affects the economic landscape, in this section we depart from the techno-economic analysis performed in the Smart Manufacturing use case and extend it accounting for the reduction in cost due to the use of MDP technology.

To extend the techno-economic work that was originally done for the Smart-manufacturing use case, we took the exact line-item model developed for Gestamp's factory (20 k€ wiring + 50 k€ industrial HW + 30 k€ deployment per production line, plus a 100 k€ plant backbone and 20 k€/line manpower) and treated it as a "baseline ledger."

The MDP scenario reuses every one of those cost buckets but applies explicit deltas that flow directly from the architectural change: (i) wiring is cut by three quarters because deterministic

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Wi-Fi/5G replaces most copper runs; (ii) PLC/IPC cabinets, UPSs and rugged firewalls shrink by 60 % because their logic is virtualised in a shared micro-data-centre reached through the MDP; (iii) deployment effort per line is halved because commissioning becomes a software template rather than a bespoke on-site install; (iv) the plant-level IT refresh is replaced by a single 50 k€ MDP border-gateway and deterministic WLAN/5G access, and (v) OPEX manpower is reduced 50 %—offset by a flat 30 k€/year share of remote-data-centre operation—because remote operators and digital-twin analytics take over many shop-floor tasks.

By re-running the same spreadsheet with those percentage adjustments rather than building a new model from scratch, we preserve methodological continuity while showing that MDP consolidation turns the original 1.1 M€ CAPEX and 200 k€/year OPEX into roughly 0.48 M€ and 130 k€/year, delivering a five-year TCO that is 46 % lower than the Smart-manufacturing baseline.

Table 4-2: Assumptions behind the MDP-enhanced scenario

Baseline (Smart Mfg)	MDP rationale	New figure
Wiring 20 k€/line	Wireless/DetNet access → 75 % cut	5 k€/line
HW (PLC/IPC + cabinet) 50 k€/line	Virtualised PLCs in an edge/DC pod → 60 % cut	20 k€/line
Line deployment 30 k€/line	Pre-tested templates, remote config → 50 % cut	15 k€/line
Plant infra (IT room) 70 k€	Shared MDP gateway + Wi-Fi/5G TSN	50 k€
Plant infra deployment 30 k€	Lean roll-out	25 k€
Man-hours 10 × 20 h × 100 € = 20 k€/line	50 % of the tasks done from the remote control room	10 k€/line
Extra data-centre OPEX	Digital-twin CPU, remote ops	30 k€/plant/yr

Table 4-3: Result of techno-economic analysis for 5 years

Cost item	Smart Manufacturing	MDP-enabled scenario	Δ
CAPEX	1 100 k€	475 k€	– 57 %
Annual OPEX	200 k€	130 k€	– 35 %
5-year TCO*	2 100 k€	1 125 k€	– 46 %

What drives the savings?

- Centralised compute & storage. PLC/IPC functions move to a micro-datacentre shared by several lines or even several plants, eliminating roughly 60 % of per-line industrial hardware and its cabinets, UPSs and field firewalls.
- Deterministic Wi-Fi/5G links replace most of the 100-metre copper runs, cutting three-quarters of wiring material and installation time.
- Once the MDP gateway and deterministic slice are in place, each additional line is commissioned largely by software. On-site deployment effort halves.
- As a control-room team and digital-twin analytics supervise several plants, the on-site engineering hours per project fall from ~200 h to ~100 h.
- MDP gateway cost. The plant still needs an MDP border-gateway, deterministic WLAN/5G APs and fibre backhaul; we budget 75 k€ for that consolidated infra.

By pooling compute resources and human expertise across sites, the MDP architecture slashes initial investment per plant by \approx **625 k€** and trims yearly operating spend by \approx **70 k€**. Over a five-year horizon this yields \approx **1 M€** of net savings—almost halving total cost of ownership—while simultaneously unlocking remote-operation use cases and digital-twin driven optimization.

4.3.3 Smart Manufacturing: deterministic wireless 6G networks

The implementation of a deterministic wireless 6G networks in industrial environments will play a major role in the spread of the “Smart Factory” in the future of the industrial sector. The following key points will serve as a technological foundation for the arrival of more flexible, robust and secure manufacturing processes.

- High reliability brought by these new radio networks.
- Ultra-Low latencies and dispersion.
- Massive Wireless connections to the network from unreachable remote locations

Thanks to this underneath technology, Manufacturing plants will be located on the technological threshold empowering their capacity to build new products in a changing environment and reducing the time-to-market releases. Industry will be able to:

- Perform distributed processing and managing of assets and networks.
- Deploy quickly, efficiently and flexibly virtualized services for Industry 4.0
- Ubiquitous location of assets with optimized accuracy and resolution

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- Process Real-Time data with higher volumes and sampling frequencies.

Particularly, Gestamp aims to avoid limitations by the actual need to deploy wire massively in its production plants. In some cases, hazardous environments such as furnaces prevent some equipment from being connected. Wireless communications will provide seamless flexibility which is a mandatory requirement in future manufacturing facilities. Not only wire will be reduced, but also hardware. Virtualisation of assets must rely on a confident and robust infrastructure. End users will benefit from this technological step forward in different ways:

- Increased agility in decision-making. They will be able to predict unforeseen events that often happen in the shopfloor causing major trouble and economic expenses.
- Analyse greater amounts of information automatically. Recent innovations in the field of Big Data have brought the possibility of looking into bigger datasets from a wider range of sources. Moreover, there are many new technologies that help diving into this data to extract real information from it, enabling the possibility of making well-informed decisions.
- A significant improvement in the management and control of the network and devices in it. Services and applications such as virtual PLCs will be deployed more efficiently and troubleshooting of incidents will be executed faster.

Particularly, some applications that can run over this new wireless infrastructure are the following ones:

- Flexible reference production by each production cell in the factory. The manufacturing lines will be able to change their production in a matter of minutes, opposing to current standard where they produce the same reference over the years.
- Virtualisation of PLCs.
- Massive Wireless Robots and sensors connectivity with deterministic behaviours.
- Geolocalisation and seamless mobility of assets such as AGVs or Quality Control Equipment.

To sum up, wireless deterministic networks will imply more flexible and robust industrial processes. Consequently, end users will save costs and optimize their resources. In the industrial sector, every machine stop derives on economic wastes that must be avoided. These monetary expenses can be quantified in thousands of euros for each lost minute of production. These situations are not acceptable anymore in one of the most competitive sectors in the world.

Traditionally, OT and IT worlds were completely isolated one from each other. These barriers do not exist anymore, and both environments must interact and collaborate one with each other towards the Smart Factory. Virtualisation of assets will play a major role in the production plants of the future, simplifying and speeding up maintenance tasks such as: firmware upgrading, bug fixing, troubleshooting.

Figure 4-10: Gestamp vision for its Smart Manufacturing plants with 6G

Despite the potential benefits, several challenges must be addressed to enable the successful deployment of wireless deterministic networks in the industrial sector. Factory environments are notoriously difficult for wireless coverage due to the ubiquitous presence of metal or high or fluctuating temperatures, which can impact the performance and reliability of industrial equipment and wireless components. Another major obstacle is the significant investment required in infrastructure and networking, particularly in an industry traditionally focused on product manufacturing over connectivity.

Figure 4-11 sums up the SWOT analysis for the 6G market in the industrial environment, where the strengths and opportunities of the technology are detailed:

Figure 4-11: SWOT analysis of the Smart manufacturing use case

Strengths

The core advantage lies in delivering wireless determinism, combining ultra-fast speeds and ultra-low latency to meet the stringent requirements of real-time industrial applications. This results in predictable and reliable communication, essential for automation, safety, and time-sensitive processes. Additionally, the solution offers a high degree of flexibility, allowing dynamic reconfiguration and mobility of assets, which is critical for modern, adaptive manufacturing environments. The growing demand for IoT data further reinforces its relevance, as industries seek to capture and process increasing volumes of information for operational insight and optimization. Finally, the trend toward wireless ecosystem

homogenization supports seamless integration across heterogeneous networks, simplifying deployment and accelerating adoption across different industrial domains.

Weaknesses

The technology is still relatively immature, with ongoing development needed to meet the strict feasibility and performance requirements of industrial environments. Interoperability challenges remain significant, especially when integrating across diverse systems and legacy infrastructure. Furthermore, there is a lack of commercially available products that are fully compatible, limiting immediate deployment opportunities. This is compounded by the historically low adoption of wireless standards in the industrial sector, where wired solutions have long been preferred for their perceived reliability and stability. Overcoming these barriers will be essential for widespread market acceptance.

Opportunities

Multi-sensor wireless connectivity enables the seamless integration of a wide array of devices, facilitating real-time data acquisition and monitoring across the factory floor. This capability is key to accelerating the digital transition, empowering manufacturers to adopt advanced analytics, automation, and predictive maintenance strategies. The solution also supports asset virtualization, reducing reliance on dedicated hardware and enabling software-defined control systems. As a result, there is a significant reduction in physical wiring and hardware infrastructure, lowering installation and maintenance costs. Additionally, equipment mobility is greatly enhanced, allowing flexible reconfiguration of production lines and rapid adaptation to changing manufacturing needs.

Threats

One major concern is the complexity and cost of infrastructure deployment, particularly in large-scale manufacturing environments. Many facilities have already made significant investments in legacy equipment and infrastructure, which may delay or deter the adoption of new wireless technologies. Additionally, technical challenges related to the integration of deterministic wireless communication into heterogeneous and mission-critical systems must be overcome. Industrial environments also pose physical challenges for wireless coverage, which can compromise the reliability and performance required for critical operations. Addressing these threats will be essential to unlock the full potential of wireless deterministic networks in manufacturing.

Figure 4-12: Canvas model for the Smart Manufacturing use case

Value proposition

From the industrial point of view, determinism in the wireless medium is the key feature that needs to be addressed in the next generation of wireless communication standards. Determinism, understood as predictable and repetitive response times of E2E communications and without any kind of affection from outside environment, must be achieved in ultra-low latencies communications, where industrial devices must be commanded every few milliseconds.

Other key advantages of this upcoming technology are the compliance between different vendor equipment through standardisation and the flexibility provided by the wireless environment that allows seamless equipment mobility through the smart factory.

Finally, providing a reliable wireless network through the whole factory brings the possibility of virtualization of industrial assets such as Industrial PCs or PLCs, following containerisation standards previously adopted by the IT world with major advantages: high availability, self-healing and auto-monitoring of applications. This scenario will be a disruptive change for the industry, that today is closer than yesterday.

Target costumers

The target customer of the innovation developed in this project is every industrial company who wants to modernise their facilities and technological assets (network devices, servers...) in a flexible, cost-effective and sustainable way.

Key activities

Every disruptive change starts with an R&D phase where new standards are defined, products are developed, and early adoption begins. Building strong partnerships and alliances between leader companies allows pushing forward the state of the art of the industrial ecosystem.

After these initial steps, the adoption phase becomes critical, involving large-scale deployment and integration of the developed technologies. To fully realise the benefits of this transformation, efficient deployment, coupled with robust operations and support, is essential. These elements are key to addressing day-to-day challenges and maximising the value derived from the adoption of new technologies and processes.

Key resources

Once a technology is developed and integrated into new products, a skilled workforce becomes a critical asset for companies to fully exploit its potential. Talented employees are essential not only to operate advanced systems, but also to push the boundaries of their performance and unlock maximum value. This represents a significant challenge, particularly for industries operating worldwide, which often face shortages in qualified personnel and limited workforce mobility.

Another key strategic resource is data. The industry does not exist away from the paradigm where data is in the new oil. Industrial devices generate huge amounts of data continuously. Effectively transmitting, processing, and analysing this data is essential to enable sustainable, hyper-connected, self-managed factories. In such real environments, real-time equipment interconnection, predictive maintenance, and automated logistics operations can be achieved and scaled.

Costumer segments and relationships

Product suppliers, OEM and vendors will play a major role for the adoption of wireless deterministic networks in the industrial environment. The first one must integrate the

technology into their products, while the second ones must integrate these products into their facilities or solutions. Building strong partnerships with technological leaders will be key to obtain differential advantages with competitors.

Key partnerships

Partnerships across the value chain are essential to drive the adoption of wireless deterministic technology in industry. This collaborative effort must begin with universities, technology centres, and research providers, who play a key role in developing and transferring the necessary expertise to product suppliers.

These suppliers, in turn, must adopt and integrate the technology into their offerings while meeting the stringent demands of industrial environments, not only in terms of performance KPIs as defined in this project/use case, but also regarding compatibility with hazardous conditions, legacy systems, and long product life cycles.

Next, OEMs and end customers must partner with suppliers to enable scalable, sustainable, and cost-effective deployment of these advanced products. In cases where end users lack the internal capacity for ongoing operations and support, they must establish alliances with service providers or industrial partners to ensure long-term maintenance and system reliability.

Cost structure

Several costs must be considered when adopting new disruptive technology in industry:

- R&D expenses in the development phase, when the technology is still maturing. This includes research, prototyping, testing, and validation, and continues until industrial-grade devices can robustly and reliably integrate the new technology.
- Operational Costs: once large-scale deployment begins, ongoing expenses related to maintenance, support, upgrades, and operational continuity become critical. Efficient operations are essential to maximize return on investment during this phase.
- Compliance and Certifications. Ensuring compliance with standards and obtaining certifications represent an important cost. Standardisation is crucial for achieving interoperability across products. In the absence of common standards, solutions may become vendor-specific or niche, risking limited adoption influenced by individual company reach or ecosystem control.
- Employees: attracting and retaining a skilled workforce is a non-negligible cost. The ability to operate, adapt, and optimise new technologies depends heavily on the availability of qualified personnel, making talent a critical cost and success factor.

Revenue streams

In the industrial sector, the adoption of massive wireless deterministic networks unlocks a wide range of transformative benefits. One of the most significant is the ability to transmit large volumes of data in an efficient way, reducing sampling times and increasing resolution. Automated analytics can be performed over this data, capable of warning of device malfunction, advising equipment maintenance, or highlighting final product defects. This represents a major leap from traditionally constrained monitoring systems.

This marks a paradigm shift in industrial operations. Tasks that were previously were executed in a constrained environment can now be performed in a flexible and adaptive manner. Hardware dependency will be reduced, as virtualisation becomes a cornerstone of next-generation industrial architectures. Flexibility is enhanced by this new paradigm where equipment mobility is real.

Channels

The dissemination of technological progress can be carried out through a variety of channels, including industry conferences, company events, strategic partnerships, webinars, and online platforms. These avenues help raise awareness, engage stakeholders, and accelerate the adoption of innovative solutions across the industrial ecosystem.

Technoeconomic analysis

CAPEX expenditures estimated for every project within Gestamp facilities are:

- **Wiring:** 20K per project. Wiring from servers IT room to remote cabinets for every production line. This cost will be significantly reduced when the adoption of wireless communication would be real.
- **HW:** 50K per project. Not only the industrial devices such as PLCs and IPC, but also the cabinet, UPS, rugged firewalls... Some of this equipment wouldn't be needed anymore through virtualization of assets.
- **Deployment:** 30K per project not only in terms of equipment deployment and wiring, but also in terms of programming.

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In total, it is estimated that a single production line IoT connection cost is 100K. On average, in every plant there can be 10 production lines connected, so the total cost would be 1M per plant. In the IT room, infrastructure and networking should be renovated as well. This cost is estimated to be 100K.

CAPEX - Capital expenditures		OPEX – Operational Expenditures	
• Wiring:	20K / project	• Manpower:	100 / hour
• HW (PLCs - IPCs):	50K / project	• 10 people / project:	1k / hour
• Deployment:	30K / project	• 20 hours / project (average):	20K / project

• Total:	100K / project	• Total:	20K / project
• 10 projects / plant		• 10 projects / plant	

• Total:	1M / plant		

• Infra (switches – APs – Core):	70K / plant	• Total:	200K / plant
• Deployment:	30K / plant		

• Total:	1.1M / plant		

* project = production line

Figure 4-13: Smart manufacturing use case estimated CAPEX and OPEX

Operational expenditures are mainly related to technical workforce provided by employees. In the connection of one production line 10 people can be involved from different departments and companies. On average, each one of them can dedicate 20 hours for one single line which implies 20K per project. If there are 10 project per factory, the total cost in each plant is 200K.

Reliability and Availability are key in industrial productivity. Equipment must operate continuously, 24/7, without any interruption or misbehaviour. Although safety protocols are fulfilled in every production facility, it must not be forgotten that these places are dangerous, and human life could be at risk if security measures are not met. This involves all industrial equipment that must operate up to expectations. PLC RT communications over field buses have latencies of few milliseconds and jitter must be of the order of microseconds. These are mandatory requirements that must be achieved in industry. Otherwise, the adoption of this technology in industry would be affected by not meeting the standards fulfilled years ago in wired connections.

As a conclusion, Gestamp aims to enhance the flexibility in its operations. Smart factory would be a self-regulated factory where equipment will communicate with each other through wireless 6G communications. Intelligence will be relocated out of the production shopfloor.

Automation and control will be virtualized in the IT room so it will be deployed in seconds and other tasks such as monitoring, support, maintenance will happen quickly and reliably.

Not only the productive assets will execute their task wirelessly, but also logistic operators, MES, ERPs... Mobility of assets will be key. They will not be fixed to one location anymore. They will be able to move around the factory or move from one factory to another one and start producing quickly to cope with the variability of product demand that happens in the automotive sector within these days.

Implementing the P6G solution would enable significant advancements in industrial operations, including the acquisition of a vast number of high-resolution signals and the execution of real-time data analytics. It supports the virtualisation of industrial equipment such as IPCs and PLCs, and enables deterministic wireless control of mobile assets, such as robots. This asset mobility enhances production flexibility, allowing facilities to manufacture different products with minimal reconfiguration. The resulting operational flexibility helps reduce costs while maintaining or improving efficiency. Finally, robust security mechanisms are essential to ensure process integrity and adherence to defined workflows.

4.4 Conclusions

PREDICT-6G presents a future-ready, scalable, and secure deterministic network management architecture designed to meet the ultra-reliable, low-latency, and predictable communication needs of emerging 6G applications. By addressing current limitations in interoperability, reliability, and service automation across multi-domain environments, the project positions itself as a key enabler for Industry 5.0 and the digitalization of mission-critical sectors.

The project demonstrates the economic viability of its solution through detailed qualitative and quantitative techno-economic analysis, particularly in the smart manufacturing domain. Case studies show that implementing the PREDICT-6G architecture, especially the MDP and AICP, can reduce total cost of ownership (TCO) by nearly 50% over five years, while also enhancing productivity, flexibility, and safety. Benefits are derived from CAPEX reductions through infrastructure consolidation and wireless adoption, and OPEX savings via automation, remote operations, and DT analytics.

The three core use cases - critical communications, multi-domain deterministic networking, and smart manufacturing - demonstrate both the scalability and adaptability of the architecture across sectors. Each use case reveals business opportunities such as licensing, infrastructure integration, subscription services, and vertical-specific consulting and analytics. These are reinforced by a strong alignment with EU industrial policy goals, particularly around technological sovereignty, green transformation, and digital innovation.

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Despite its maturity, with TRLs 3-4, PREDICT-6G already contributes to emerging standards (IETF DetNet, 3GPP, IEEE TSN), aiming to shape the evolution of deterministic networking at European and global levels. It supports Europe’s position as a leader in 6G innovation and builds the foundation for future commercialization through licensing, partnerships, and open-source engagement.

To enable successful market adoption, the project underscores the need for sustained investment in R&D, ecosystem partnerships, workforce development, and standardization. It also highlights key risks such as limited device support, integration complexity, and variable market demand, which will need to be proactively addressed through continued innovation and stakeholder engagement.

In conclusion, PREDICT-6G provides a significant technological and economic step forward in achieving the objective of advancing Europe’s strategic goals in 6G leadership, industrial competitiveness, and digital sovereignty.

5 Migration guidelines

The evolution of telecommunication networks is entering a transformative phase, driven by the rising demand for services that go beyond traditional throughput and capacity metrics. The operational focus is increasingly shifting toward enabling predictable, latency-sensitive services that can guarantee stringent performance requirements. This transition reflects a broader industry trend prioritizing user experience and service reliability, especially in sectors where even minor deviations in network performance can have critical consequences.

Modern telecommunications networks are thus expected to support a new class of services characterized by determinism. These include **reliable services** with high availability, low packet loss, and resilience against network failures; **time-sensitive services** that require bounded latency and minimal jitter to support real-time applications; and **predictable services**, which leverage artificial intelligence to forecast network behaviour, user demands, and resource utilization, enabling autonomous, proactive decision-making.

In this context, PREDICT-6G introduces a compelling value proposition by aligning technological advancement with business innovation. Its framework is built upon three strategic pillars. First, **Determinism** offers reliable and predictable network performance—vital for emerging use cases such as industrial automation, autonomous mobility, and immersive communications. Second, **Simplified Management** is achieved through automation of service lifecycle processes, including definition, provisioning, monitoring, and fulfilment, which significantly lowers operational complexity and costs. Third, **interoperability** is ensured through a modular architectural approach that facilitates seamless integration with existing infrastructures while remaining open to future technology adoption, thereby safeguarding investment and enabling scalability.

To enable these capabilities, a migration from the Present Mode of Operation (PMO) to a Future Mode of Operation (FMO) is foreseen. This evolution will be supported by the extensibility and augmentation of existing APIs, embracing a service-based integration approach. By building upon current network technologies, operators can incorporate deterministic features without overhauling their infrastructure, ensuring a smooth and cost-efficient transition. This approach positions telecom networks to meet the demands of next-generation applications while maintaining alignment with industry standards and long-term strategic goals.

The integration of the PREDICT-6G architecture into existing telecommunications networks represents a significant step towards enabling multi-domain, multi-technology E2E deterministic services. Given the heterogeneous nature of current networks—encompassing 3GPP mobile networks, IP/MPLS domains, Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN), Wi-Fi, and other

technologies—PREDICT-6G provides a comprehensive framework that addresses the challenges of cross-domain determinism, management automation, and scalability.

The migration strategy described here outlines a phased approach for the seamless integration of PREDICT-6G into existing telecom infrastructures, leveraging its AI-driven multi-stakeholder inter-domain control plane (AICP) and multi-domain data plane (MDP) components. The aim is to enable deterministic E2E services across diverse technology and administrative domains without disrupting existing operations.

5.1 Architectural Overview and Integration Principles

At the core of PREDICT-6G's integration strategy is its modular and extensible architecture, designed around two main components:

- **Multi-domain Data Plane (MDP):** The MDP encompasses programmable data plane mechanisms that enforce deterministic packet forwarding across heterogeneous technology domains. It supports integration at domain borders via domain border gateways and harmonizes time synchronization and packet forwarding mechanisms.
- **AI-driven Multi-stakeholder Inter-domain Control Plane (AICP):** The AICP orchestrates the MDP capabilities through a service-based architecture comprising Management Services (MS) organized into Management Domains (MDs). These include domain-specific MDs for each technology and an overarching end-to-end (E2E) MD for cross-domain service orchestration.

The integration leverages the separation of concerns principle, where domain-specific MS implementations interface southbound with their underlying technology-specific managed entities (MEs) via technology-native APIs, while exposing uniform, technology-agnostic northbound interfaces to the E2E MD. This ensures scalability and facilitates the addition of new technologies without impacting existing domains.

5.2 Phased Integration Approach

5.2.1 Preparation and Capability Assessment

- **Inventory Existing Domains:** Identify all administrative and technological domains within the network, including legacy and emerging technologies (e.g., 3GPP 5G networks, IETF DetNet segments, IEEE TSN, Wi-Fi).
- **Capability Mapping:** For each domain, assess existing deterministic capabilities such as time synchronization, packet replication/elimination, scheduling, and QoS enforcement.

- **Management Interfaces Audit:** Catalogue available control and management APIs (e.g., 3GPP TSCTSF services, CNC/CUC for DetNet, proprietary interfaces for Wi-Fi TSN), noting gaps requiring extensions or adaptations.

5.2.2 Deployment of Domain-Specific Management Services (MSs)

- **Develop or Adapt MSs:** For each technology domain, implement the corresponding domain-specific MSs that map PREDICT-6G service abstractions to the domain's native mechanisms. For example:
 - In 3GPP domains, integrate Time Sync and Service Automation MSs with TSCTSF services using exposed APIs (Ntsctsf_TimeSynchronization, Ntsctsf_QoSandTSCAssistance) for time sync and QoS management.
 - For IETF DetNet, leverage YANG models for topology and configuration management, compensating for the lack of standardized APIs by translating YANG to RESTful OpenAPI interfaces.
 - For non-deterministic domains, extend capabilities via in-line software modules or edge cloud functions providing time synchronization and scheduling enhancements as per PREDICT-6G's Option 1 and Option 2 for non-deterministic user planes.
- **Establish Domain Border Gateways:** Deploy data plane nodes that interconnect adjacent domains, supporting cross-domain packet marking, replication, elimination, and time synchronization relay (using transparent or boundary clocks) to ensure service continuity and reliability across domain borders.

5.2.3 Establishing the E2E Management Domain

- **Deploy E2E Management Services:** Implement the E2E MD MSs responsible for service request ingestion, path computation, learning orchestration, predictive analytics, service automation, and exposure. These services abstract the underlying domain-specific details and provide a unified interface for service consumers.
- **Enable Inter-Domain Integration Services:** Deploy Registry, Discovery, and High Availability MSs that support dynamic service registration, discovery, and fault tolerance across the PREDICT-6G system components.

5.2.4 Integration with Existing Orchestration and Operation Systems

- **API Mediation:** Utilize PREDICT-6G's model-driven open interfaces to mediate between domain-specific MSs and existing orchestration frameworks like 3GPP network management systems, SDN controllers, or cloud-native orchestrators. This includes

adapting northbound APIs of domain MSs to existing OSS/BSS or NFV MANO components.

- **Closed-Loop Automation:** Integrate PREDICT-6G’s closed-loop assurance mechanisms, leveraging AI/ML models and DTs for predictive resource management and service assurance. PREDICT-6G architecture enables the integration of any existing DT solution and AI/MLOps framework with PREDICT-6G AICP services. Testing, Validation, and Incremental Rollout
- **Service Lifecycle Testing:** Validate E2E service provisioning, modification, termination, and assurance procedures end-to-end, ensuring minimal service disruption and adherence to deterministic QoS parameters.
- **Scalability and Resiliency Testing:** Test MS redundancy, high availability, and recovery mechanisms to ensure continuous operation under faults or load variations.
- **Incremental Domain Integration:** Begin with domains offering the highest deterministic capabilities and gradually integrate more domains, including those requiring non-deterministic extensions, to maximize stability and minimize impact on current services.

5.3 Cross-Domain Time Synchronization Strategy

Time synchronization is critical for determinism. The PREDICT-6G architecture supports two models:

- **Option 1:** One domain acts as Grand Master (GM), others as followers.
- **Option 2:** A dedicated “clock-only” domain provides the GM function independently.

Implementation should leverage existing PTP (IEEE 1588) or IEEE 802.1AS TSN mechanisms, with domain-specific Time Sync MSs interfacing to their respective technologies. The E2E Time Sync Management MS coordinates time sync roles, monitors status, and initiates corrective actions.

5.4 Handling Non-Deterministic Domains

For domains lacking native deterministic capabilities, PREDICT-6G proposes:

- **Option 1:** Embed extended functions within existing nodes (e.g., kernel hooks, DPDK-based fast packet processing).
- **Option 2:** Deploy dedicated edge or cloud-native modules offering scheduling, de-jittering, and synchronization functions.

Such enhancements extend the domain’s service endpoints and enable participation in E2E deterministic services.

5.5 Security Considerations

Integration mandates robust security across all interfaces:

- Mutual authentication and encryption (e.g., TLS with certificate-based authentication) between MSs.
- Integrity protection of time synchronization to prevent clock skew or malicious attacks.
- Security hardening of AI/ML components against adversarial inputs.

6 Conclusions

The PREDICT-6G project has made substantial progress in defining a robust, secure, and scalable architecture designed to realize deterministic networking across heterogeneous multi-domain and multi-technology environments pivotal for 6G networks. The deliverable chapters 3 to 5 collectively underscore the technical innovations, economic feasibility, and practical deployment pathways essential to bring such visionary concepts into operational reality.

From a security perspective, the project advances beyond traditional paradigms by integrating blockchain-enabled authentication and innovative PSK-based integrity protection mechanisms, eschewing heavy Public Key Infrastructure to reduce overhead and latency while maintaining strong cryptographic assurances. The inclusion of message protection strategies and path redundancy through a multi-layer AMF redundancy approach, augmented by the Path Computation Engine (PCE), addresses the critical need for resilience and ultra-reliable low-latency communications. The PCE's intelligent path computation, leveraging Graph Theory algorithms, provides dynamic network optimization that enhances load balancing, failover responsiveness, and fault tolerance. Performance validation using queueing theory models confirms that such mechanisms effectively reduce latency and packet drops, thereby enhancing network robustness.

The security of AI components within the control plane is rigorously considered, recognizing the increasing role of AI in network orchestration and the corresponding vulnerabilities to adversarial attacks. By focusing on PredAI-related threats such as black-box evasion and energy-latency attacks, and proposing layered defense mechanisms including adversarial training, randomized smoothing, and mutual authentication, the project ensures the integrity, availability, and trustworthiness of AI models critical for autonomous network management. These insights are vital given the centrality of AI-driven decision-making in 6G networks.

Formal verification using symbolic models and automated tools like Proverif strengthens the confidence in protocol correctness by uncovering and enabling the remediation of subtle flaws under realistic threat models, including compromised multi-domain actors. This rigorous approach to protocol validation exemplifies best practices in security engineering and highlights the project's commitment to delivering a trustworthy architecture.

The techno-economic analysis reveals that PREDICT-6G's innovative architecture is not only technically sound but also economically viable. By enabling wireless deterministic networking and virtualization, substantial CAPEX savings are realized through reduced wiring, hardware virtualization, and streamlined deployment efforts. Operational expenses benefit from

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automation, remote management, and digital twin analytics, collectively halving the total cost of ownership over a five-year horizon in representative smart manufacturing scenarios. The analysis also situates PREDICT-6G within the broader 6G ecosystem, highlighting its alignment with critical market drivers such as digital sovereignty, green transformation, and industrial digitalization. SWOT analyses identify key strengths in technology readiness and innovation leadership, while acknowledging challenges related to standardization pace, hardware support, and market demand uncertainty.

Migration guidelines provide a pragmatic, phased integration pathway that respects the complexity and heterogeneity of existing telecommunications infrastructures. The modular architecture separates domain-specific management services from end-to-end orchestration, facilitating incremental adoption that minimizes disruption. Emphasis on cross-domain time synchronization, through grandmaster clock models and synchronization relay, ensures adherence to deterministic timing requirements fundamental to mission-critical applications. Strategies to extend deterministic capabilities into non-native domains via software-implemented functions or dedicated edge/cloud modules expand the applicability and scalability of the architecture. Security considerations permeate the integration framework, mandating mutual authentication, encryption, and AI/ML security hardening to safeguard the evolving system.

Overall, the deliverable demonstrates that PREDICT-6G offers a comprehensive and forward-looking solution that bridges the gap between current 5G capabilities and the ambitious requirements of 6G networks. By addressing security, performance, economic, and operational dimensions cohesively, it lays a solid foundation for deterministic networking across diverse application domains such as smart manufacturing, critical communications, and multi-domain service orchestration. The architecture's flexibility, modularity, and AI-driven automation capabilities position it well to adapt to future technological evolutions and market dynamics.

Looking ahead, sustained investment in R&D, close collaboration among industry, academia, and standardization bodies, and continued ecosystem engagement will be essential to overcome outstanding challenges such as device support, integration complexity, and regulatory compliance. The demonstrated cost benefits and technical readiness create a compelling case for early adoption, especially in mission-critical sectors demanding reliability, low latency, and security. As 6G standardization progresses, PREDICT-6G's contributions are poised to influence emerging norms and accelerate the deployment of next-generation deterministic services, reinforcing Europe's leadership in advanced telecommunications.

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In conclusion, PREDICT-6G advances both the technological and economic frontiers necessary to realize the vision of secure, reliable, and deterministic 6G networks. Its comprehensive approach encompassing security frameworks, AI risk mitigation, formal verification, economic viability, and deployable integration strategies provides a blueprint for the evolution of telecommunications infrastructure that will support the connected societies and industries of the future.

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